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Deployment and upgrading toolkits and recommendations for OJS and Lodel

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Abstract	<p>This toolkit is a comprehensive resource developed within the CRAFT-OA project to support the conception, deployment, and long-term maintenance of institutional publishing services. Written for platform managers and technical staff of institutional publishing service as well as tools and technology providers. It spans strategic, operational, and technical dimensions of service creation and sustainability.</p> <p>It offers practical guidance from initial scoping and design through day-to-day operations and ongoing improvement. It can be used as a full handbook or consulted selectively to resolve specific issues, with each chapter concluding with concise takeaways and action lists.</p> <p>The content covers foundations for new services, adding journals, staffing and role design, effort and cost considerations for launch and continuity, identifiers, policies and rights. Platform choice is treated in depth, with extensive, hands-on guidance for OJS. An annex introduces Lodel 2.0 with preliminary installation steps and a “Hello World” bundle.</p>

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List of Acronyms

AAM	Author Accepted Manuscript
API	Application Programming Interface
ARK	Archival Resource Key
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution license
CLEO	Centre for Open Electronic Publishing (Centre pour l'édition électronique ouverte)
CLI	Command Line Interface
CLOCKSS	Controlled Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe
CMS	Content Management System
COPE	Committee on Publication Ethics
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
DB	Database
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DISCO	Discoverability Companion
DMARC	Domain-based Message Authentication, Reporting, and Conformance
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals

DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DONA	Digital Object Numbering Authority
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EDIB	Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging
ePUB	Electronic Publication
FOSS	Free and Open-Source Software
DKIM	DomainKeys Identified Mail
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
ICANN	Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers
ID	Identifier
IDF	International DOI Foundation
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
IPTP	Institutional Publishing Tools and Technology Provider
ISNI	International Standard Name Identifier
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation

ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
IT	Information Technology
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite
JMS	Journal Management System
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LAMP	Linux, Apache, MySQL/MariaDB, PHP
LOCKSS	Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe
LODEL	Electronic publishing software (Logiciel d'édition électronique)
LTS	Long-Term Support
OAI	Open Archives Initiative
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association
OCLC	Online Computer Library Center
OJS	Open Journal Systems
OLH	Open Library of Humanities
OMP	Open Monograph Press
OA	Open Access
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PDF	Portable Document Format
PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor

PID	Persistent Identifier
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
PKP PN	Public Knowledge Project Preservation Network
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
ROR	Research Organisation Registry
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SIG	Special Interest Group
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
SPF	Sender Policy Framework
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSH	Secure Shell
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SWHID	Software Heritage Identifiers
SWORD	Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TSV	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (Tieteellisten Seurain Valtuuskunta)
UAB	Autonomous University of Barcelona (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona)
UI	User Interface

URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UX	User Experience
VM	Virtual Machine
VoR	Version of Record
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WAMP	Windows, Apache, MySQL/MariaDB, PHP
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current toolkit is a practical, structured guide to the full lifecycle of planning, launching, and sustaining institutional publishing services. Developed within the CRAFT-OA project, it consolidates the common questions and decision points that platform managers and technical staff of institutional publishing service providers and technology providers, and publishers encounter when building or maintaining a service. Its objective is to streamline setup and operations by providing clear, consistently organised answers to recurring issues, from initial concept through ongoing maintenance.

Presented in a structured format, the Toolkit is designed for flexible use: it can be read end-to-end or consulted as a reference to address specific needs at any stage of a service's evolution. Each section concludes with a checklist to accelerate decision-making and implementation. The Toolkit is planned to be maintained as a living document (within the [Publisher's Living Handbook for Diamond Open Access](#), a Key Exploitable Result (KER) of the CRAFT-OA project) that will adapt to future scenarios and incorporate reader feedback via the designated contact channel.

The scope spans strategic, operational, and technical dimensions. Core sections guide the formulation of requirements and ideas for both services and journals, define team structures and human resources, estimate the efforts needed to start and sustain operations, and address identifiers along with policies and rights. The topic of journal management systems is covered in depth, with a substantial focus on the software Open Journal Systems (OJS), including hardware requirements, hosting models, infrastructure choices, single versus multi-journal installations, theming, role definitions, installation, maintenance, upgrades, and recommended plugins. An annex provides preliminary installation guidance for the software Lodel 2.0, including a "Hello World" bundle.

By bringing together actionable guidance, concise summaries, and checklists, the Toolkit reduces risk and effort, lays out responsibilities and resource needs, and supports consistent, sustainable operations.

2 ABOUT THE TOOLKIT

Context

This document has been written in the framework of the CRAFT-OA project by editorial service experts. It is designed as a living document that can be adapted to future scenarios and improved with input from readers.

Objective

This toolkit aims to cover the common questions that need to be asked for the creation and maintenance of an institutional publishing service.

Target audience

The toolkit has been written for platform managers and technical staff of institutional publishing service providers (IPSPs), institutional publishing tools and technology providers (IPTPs), and publishers. This toolkit includes general sections related to starting a service and sections specific to publishing platforms.

Usage and Format

There are many ways to use this toolkit. It can be read in its entirety, or used as a reference to answer specific questions that may arise at different points in the life of the service. Each section can either be read in full or you can simply refer to the final summary and checklist for a concise overview.

The toolkit adopts a modular, consistently structured design. Content provides concise, self-contained guidance focused on key decisions and actions, supported by a checkbox concept to help track readiness and progress. Where useful, sections include brief summaries, checklists, and links to further resources.

3 INSTITUTIONAL PUBLISHING SERVICES

This section deals with platform-agnostic topics. It focuses on the strategic, organisational, and operational aspects common to all institutional publishing services. The aim is to provide a foundation that supports decision-making and planning before any platform-specific implementation.

✓ REQUIREMENTS AND IDEA FOR A NEW SERVICE

Before setting up a new service, it is necessary to reflect on its goals and framework conditions. Consider your target group(s), the resources you will have at your disposal, and your client (if there is one). See [Institutional publishing services: Requirements and Idea for a new Journal](#)

1. Initial Planning and Reasoning

When establishing a new service, it is essential to first ensure that there is a genuine need for it and that you have the capacity and resources to maintain it over time. If the service is set up on behalf of a third party—such as an institution or a learned society—a clearly defined mission and an official mandate to proceed are necessary.

It is equally important to gain a solid understanding of the target audience. Their composition, needs, and expectations must be analysed. This foundational knowledge will help design a service that is both relevant and sustainable.

2. Service Scope and Definition

Defining the service scope is crucial, whether it provides technical hosting, full publishing, or editorial support. It should clearly specify who the eligible users are and what fees apply, and transparency should be ensured by publishing costs and financial reports. If the service is free, this must be explicitly stated to avoid any confusion.

Service efficiency should be estimated by projecting the number of journals and their expected annual issue output, aiding capacity and resource planning.

The chosen software should meet the service goals, whether a hosted solution or an in-house platform, as this impacts long-term sustainability and control. The hardware infrastructure must be reliable, scalable, secure, and support backups and performance. For further guidance, see [Institutional publishing services: Choosing a Platform](#), [OJS: Hosting options](#), [OJS: Hardware Requirements](#)

Free and Open-Source Software (FOSS) best practices should be considered when customising software by avoiding core code changes; instead, use plugins or themes to preserve stability and upgradeability. Set up a sustainable service architecture with separate test, development, and live environments.

3. Organisational Structure and Governance

When operating a publishing service on behalf of a third party, a clear mission and secure formal mandate needs to be established. This mandate should define the purpose, responsibilities, and scope of the service. The composition of the operating team should align with the defined service model. This involves assessing available personnel, determining whether team members are permanent staff or project-based, and identifying relevant expertise in areas such as publishing workflows and technical infrastructure. To ensure transparency and maintain quality standards, clear selection criteria should be developed, specifying who is eligible to publish and what content is appropriate. Additionally, establishing a scientific advisory board or selection committee can support editorial decision-making and uphold the integrity and focus of the publishing service.

4. Identity and Communication

A consistent design theme across journals supports building a recognisable digital identity, improving user experience (UX) and platform visibility. To share a positive reputation between journals and reduce costs, a common practice is using a single design theme with only small modifications for different journals, but exceptions can be made if considered worth the effort. The name of the service and the domain name should be unique. The responsibility for the domain should be held by the publishing institution.

5. Policies and Legal Aspects

Beyond technical and operational planning, clear policies should be established governing the service. A key policy might be Diamond Open Access (OA), requiring no fees for authors or readers. Policies should address content licensing, editorial standards, peer review, and ethics to ensure transparency, consistency, and trust. They should also reference OA principles, intellectual property, and academic integrity. For further reading, see [Institutional publishing services: Policies & Rights](#).

The legal framework must ensure trademark compliance for names and logos, with contracts defining roles and rights of editors, authors, and administrators. It should cover OA adherence, copyright, Creative Commons licenses, and privacy laws like General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). A solid legal foundation is vital for the service's credibility and sustainability.

6. Economic and Operational Sustainability

A sustainability model ensures the long-term operation and growth of the service by addressing financial, organisational, and technical aspects.

Financial sustainability can be achieved through institutional support, public funding, grants, or in-kind contributions—avoiding author or reader fees in line with Diamond OA principles. Clear budgeting and transparent cost reporting build stakeholder trust. If any fees apply, they must be clearly published along with regular financial reports. If the service is free, this should be explicitly stated.

Organisational sustainability relies on stable governance structures, such as advisory boards or steering committees, and clearly defined roles and responsibilities.

The sustainability model should align available resources with the service's goals to ensure continued relevance and resilience. Also see [Institutional publishing services: Efforts for Starting and Sustaining](#).

7. Preservation and Evaluation

An effective archiving strategy is essential for the long-term preservation and accessibility of published content. Collaborating with trusted preservation services—such as the Public Knowledge Project Preservation Network (PKP PN) for journals using Open Journal Systems (OJS)—can provide reliable, automated archiving. Additional partnerships with national libraries or institutional repositories can strengthen the resilience and visibility of the archive.

Evaluating service quality is equally important. The Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) offers a robust framework for maintaining high standards in governance, transparency, editorial practices, and technical infrastructure. Regular self-assessments using the DOAS tool help track progress, identify areas for improvement, and ensure alignment with best practices.

Summary

Before launching a new service, it is essential to clarify its purpose, target users, and operational framework. This is a summary of key steps: assessing demand, defining scope, legal considerations, infrastructure, sustainability, and quality assurance. It serves as a structured guide to plan and implement a viable and coherent service.

Checklist

1. Initial Planning and Reasoning

- Verify the need for the service and ensure you can maintain it.
- Understand the target group's composition and needs.
- Estimate expected service use: number of journals, issues, and timeline.
- Align target group needs with your team's capabilities.

2. Service Scope and Definition

- Define the scope of the service (e.g. hosting, publishing, editorial work).
- List services offered, eligibility, and user costs. Publish costs and accounts regularly.
- Choose appropriate software; decide on self-maintained vs hosted solution.
- Review: [OJS: Choosing a Platform](#).
- Review: [OJS: Hosting options](#).
- Review [OJS: Hardware Requirements](#).

- Estimate required hardware capacity.
- Avoid modifying core software code; use plugins or themes for changes.
- Establish a sustainable service architecture: test, development, and live servers.

3. Organisational Structure and Governance

- If acting for a third party, agree on a clear mission and obtain a mandate.
- Build your operational team based on the defined service and available expertise.
- Set clear selection criteria for publishing; consider advisory or selection board.

4. Identity and Communication

- Design a recognisable digital identity; reuse design with minor adaptations if possible.
- Create a unique name and register a domain; keep institutional control of the domain.

5. Policies and Legal Aspects

- Define comprehensive policies (e.g. Diamond OA as baseline).
- Address legal aspects: trademarks, licenses, privacy, OA, etc.

6. Economic and Operational Sustainability

- Develop a sustainability model. Refer to [Institutional publishing services: Efforts for Starting and Sustaining](#).
- List services offered, eligibility, and user costs. Publish costs and accounts regularly.

7. Preservation and Evaluation

- Plan long-term archiving (e.g. PKP PN, Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe (LOCKSS), national libraries).
- Define service quality. The DOAS standard can help (apply its self-assessment tool periodically).

Additional resources

- ❖ DOAS:
<https://toolsuite.diamas.org/diamond-open-access-standard-doas>
→ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15227981>
- ❖ DOAS self-assessment tool:
<https://diamas.fecyt.es/>
- ❖ IPSP Guidelines:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13786094>
- ❖ IPSP Toolsuite:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14001342>
- ❖ PKP PN:
<https://pkp.sfu.ca/pkp-pn/>

- ❖ Open Access Journals Toolkit (DOAJ & OASPA, 2024):
<https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/>

✓ REQUIREMENTS AND IDEA FOR A NEW JOURNAL

Before adding a new journal to your institutional publishing service, it is necessary to ensure that its inclusion is editorially and strategically justified. A new title should strengthen the service's profile, contribute to the institution's research strategy, and comply with existing editorial and technical frameworks. Careful consideration of editorial readiness, technical setup, operational sustainability, and long-term preservation is essential for a successful onboarding process.

1. Preliminary Considerations

Launching a new journal requires clear editorial and strategic reasoning. The editorial team must be ready to publish, with defined workflows, roles, and editorial policies in place.

A new title should fill a relevant disciplinary or institutional gap—either by serving an underrepresented academic field, offering a Diamond OA alternative, or improving the publishing experience for authors.

Before proceeding, assess the journal's academic justification and ensure that it aligns with the institution's mission and open science principles. It is also advisable to direct the editorial team to relevant Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS) resources on [editorial management](#), [research integrity](#), [ownership and governance](#) to support best practices from the outset.

2. Technical and Operational Setup

A successful integration of a new journal requires careful planning of its technical and operational configuration. Discussions with the editorial team should clarify what types of content will be supported, such as traditional articles, multimedia (video, audio), or data publications. The accepted submission languages and the journal's website language must be defined in advance to ensure accessibility and clarity.

Licensing policies are another crucial aspect. The journal should adopt licenses compatible with institutional and OA standards (e.g. Creative Commons). Funding models—whether institutional support, publication fees, or external grants—must be transparent and sustainable. Refer to [Institutional publishing services: Efforts for Starting and Sustaining](#) for guidance on identifying costs such as staff workload, technical maintenance, and digital preservation.

Technical compatibility with the institutional infrastructure must be verified, especially if using a shared publishing platform such as OJS. Long-term maintenance, including regular software updates and security patches, must be accounted for in planning (see [OJS: Maintenance](#) and [OJS: Upgrade](#)).

If the journal will use the institution's provided submission system, ensure it supports the chosen review model and editorial workflows. If not, verify that an alternative submission and review process is in place.

All copyright and licensing metadata should comply with institutional and repository policies to facilitate indexing and reuse.

The journal's website and visual identity should follow institutional design standards unless a distinct but coherent visual profile is justified. Layout consistency between website and article formats enhances usability and recognisability.

Domain name strategy is another early decision: choose whether the journal will operate under the service's subdomain or maintain an independent domain. The institution should retain control of the registration and renewal process to ensure stability.

Digital preservation and archiving strategies must be established from the start—using, for example, LOCKSS, Controlled Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe (CLOCKSS), or institutional repositories. Define clear access policies, version control procedures, and long-term archiving mechanisms to guarantee the durability of published content.

Persistent identifiers are essential for ensuring scholarly connectivity. Encourage or require the use of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for articles, Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) Identifiers (IDs) for authors, Research Organisation Registry (ROR) identifiers for institutions, and Funder IDs for grant recognition. For further guidance, see [Institutional publishing services: Identifiers](#).

Identify target indexes (such as Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), Scopus, or Web of Science) and consult the [Catalog of documentations about Scholarly Publications Indexes](#) to verify technical and metadata requirements in advance. Support the editorial team in preparing compliant metadata, and advise on applying for an International Standard Serial Number (ISSN) once the first issue is published.

In addition to scholarly indexing, consider the journal's visibility in general search engines. Implementing basic Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) practices (using structured metadata, descriptive titles, clear Uniform Resource Locators (URLs), and consistent use of keywords) will improve the discoverability of articles through platforms like Google and Google Scholar. Ensure that the journal website supports standard metadata schemas (e.g. Dublin Core, schema.org) and provides a sitemap to facilitate automated indexing.

Summary

Before adding a new journal to your institutional publishing service, ensure it is editorially and strategically justified. Technical, operational, and sustainability aspects must be reviewed in advance. This checklist outlines key steps to guide the onboarding process efficiently.

Checklist

1. Preliminary Considerations

- Confirm that the journal is editorially ready to launch.
- Ensure there is a clear academic and/or institutional rationale for launching the journal.
- Verify the journal fills a disciplinary gap, offers an OA alternative, or improves the publishing experience for authors.
- Direct the editorial team to the DIAMAS resources on [editorial management](#), [research integrity](#), [ownership and governance](#).

2. Technical and Operational Setup

- Discuss with the journal the types of content to be supported (e.g. video, audio, other media).
- Confirm the accepted submission languages and the language of the journal website.
- Define the types of article licenses to be accepted.
- Determine the journal's funding model (institutional support, APCs, grants). See [Institutional publishing services: Efforts for Starting and Sustaining](#).
- Account for hidden costs: technical resources, staff workload, digital preservation strategies. Refer to [Institutional publishing services: Efforts for Starting and Sustaining](#).
- Ensure technical compatibility with the existing infrastructure (e.g. OJS).
- Plan for long-term maintenance and software updates (see [OJS: Maintenance](#) and [OJS: Upgrade](#)).
- Configure the submission system to support article intake and peer review workflows, or make sure there is an alternative submission workflow in place.
- Implement copyright and licensing metadata in line with institutional policies.
- Align journal design with institutional standards or define a unique visual identity.
- Ensure consistency in website and article layout design.
- Decide on the domain name strategy (subdomain of the service or standalone domain).
- Implement a robust digital preservation and archiving strategy (e.g. LOCKSS, CLOCKSS, institutional repositories).
- Define access policies and version control procedures.
- Facilitate the use of persistent identifiers (DOI, Archival Resource Key (ARK), ORCID iD, ROR, Funder DOIs/ Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)). See [Institutional publishing services: Identifiers](#).

- Identify intended scholarly indexes (e.g. DOAJ, Scopus, Web of Science – check the [Catalog of documentations about Scholarly Publications Indexes](#)).
- Verify technical requirements for each target index.
- Check and communicate metadata requirements for indexing services and repositories.
- Support or guide the journal in applying for an ISSN after the first issue.
- Enhance search engine visibility through SEO: use structured metadata, clear titles and URLs, consistent keywords, standard schemas (e.g. Dublin Core, schema.org), and a sitemap.

Additional resources

- ❖ Introduction: Getting Found, Staying Found, Increasing Impact: Enhancing Readership and Preserving Content for OJS Journals, Second Edition:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/getting-found-staying-found/en/>
- ❖ Index Application Guide:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/indexing-guide/en/>
- ❖ How to Start or Flip Fully OA Journals: Academy-owned publisher guide:
<https://blog.scholasticahq.com/post/how-to-start-flip-open-access-academic-journal/#promote>
- ❖ DIAMAS - ToolSuite - Editorial management:
<https://toolsuite.diamas.org/editorial-management>
- ❖ DIAMAS - ToolSuite - Research integrity:
<https://toolsuite.diamas.org/research-integrity>
- ❖ DIAMAS - ToolSuite - Ownership and governance:
<https://toolsuite.diamas.org/ownership-and-governance>
- ❖ Catalog of documentations about Scholarly Publications Indexes:
<https://github.com/operas-eu/craft-oa-SchollIndexes-doc>

✓ SERVICE TEAM AND HUMAN RESOURCES

The roles required to run a service largely depend on your objectives as a publishing service, and no two services are the same, so teams will differ. It is common for these objectives to change over time or to be expanded or reduced according to budget or strategic guidelines.

For example, one service may focus on providing state-of-the-art technological tools and leave issues such as indexing for later. Another service may prioritise typesetting and delegate editorial criteria to the journals or external teams.

For this reason, we won't prescribe the exact team you should build in this section, but we will instead list the most common roles in service teams. Keep in mind that a role is a task and that a person can perform several tasks at the same time. This is because some roles involve more work than others and some professional profiles are capable of performing several roles at the same time.

- **Head of service:** Sets a mission and policies and ensures both are upheld, coordinates resources (human and physical), providing them if they are not sufficient. They must have an overview of scientific publications, the institution and open science.
- **Journal coordinator:** Coordinates full service for journals and assesses/approves new additions. Defines the quality standards to be required of all journals. Plans actions (training, updates, indexing, etc.).
- Must be aware of trends in academic publishing and open science. In some publication services, this role may be also partially performed by a scientific board which will review and assess/approve journal applications. In some services, this role may also include editorial platform management tasks.
- **Technology manager:** Analyses, designs and implements the technological infrastructure on which the service's activity is based. Must have knowledge of both systems and development in order to execute or delegate related tasks. If the workload is high or the tasks are complex, you may need specialised system administration and/or development roles to support this professional.
- **Support:** Provides functional and/or technical support for the service tools. This team member must be an expert in the use of the tools and know the editorial processes to attend to the demands of the feedback and/or refer to the technical service. This help may include training to the editorial & publishing chain.
- **Visibility manager:** Monitors the visibility of the journals in indexers and alternative metrics. Proposes actions for improvement (changes in journal strategies, applying to new indexes, SEO...).
- **Metadata manager:** Monitors the quality and completeness of the metadata published by journal managers at the source and in the upstreams.

Additional roles are essential to service operations, e.g Translators, Typesetters, Designers (paper, digital, and web), and Proofreaders. Assess whether to staff them in-house, contract them externally, or delegate responsibility to individual journals to manage and/or outsource them.

To provide context for decision-making, we present anonymised examples of resource configurations from real services:

Gutenberg's Lost Papers operates an institutional service that hosts its 20 journals with an external provider that supplies publishing management tools. Layout, proofreading and translation are also outsourced, though coordinated by the service. The service ensures editorial quality and focuses on dissemination, visibility and metadata curation. Its team includes a Head of Service, a Journal Coordinator and a Visibility Manager who is also responsible for metadata. Technical support is also outsourced and no in-house development is undertaken.

The *University of Ada Lovelace* runs an institutional service that maintains its own infrastructure and provides layout design and proofreading. Without a dedicated visibility and metadata role, these responsibilities are delegated to library staff and journal editorial teams. To support 50 journals, the team comprises a Head of Service, a Journal Coordinator, a Typesetter, a part-time Technician, a Proofreader, and an English Translator (with other languages outsourced). The coordinator, typesetter, and technician rotate to deliver support and training to editorial committees.

Summary

To organise a publishing service, it is essential to set clear objectives, decide which functions will be internal or outsourced, and assign key roles to ensure coordination, technology, support, visibility, and content quality while adapting the team to budget and workload.

Checklist

- Identify the service's priority objectives (technology, quality, dissemination).
- Decide which tasks are handled in-house and which are outsourced.
- Assign overall coordination and strategic planning.
- Ensure technical infrastructure and maintenance.
- Provide support for editorial tools and processes.
- Define visibility and indexing management.
- Secure metadata control and quality.
- Cover complementary services (translation, typesetting, design, proofreading) as needed.
- Plan training and updates for teams.
- Align the budget with the service's structure and scope.

✓ EFFORTS FOR STARTING AND SUSTAINING

Running a new publishing service requires careful financial planning. In communications with participating journals, ensure that they have a business model for sustainability in place, whether it is APC-based or a diamond model. If the editorial team needs advice, you can forward them to the article on [funding](#). As an institutional publisher, you will have to make some key considerations for the initial setup and ongoing operational costs.

Initial Costs

The first year of a journal's life cycle involves significant investment in time, resources, and financial planning.

- **Consulting and Planning** – Expert guidance on publishing workflows, legal considerations, and indexing requirements.
- **Hardware and Infrastructure** – Servers, backup systems, and other IT infrastructure.
- **Setup Costs** – Customisation and configuration of the publishing platform.
- **Theme, Template, and Design** – Ensuring the journal's website and article layouts meet branding and usability standards.
- **Custom Plugins and Features** – Development of additional functionalities specific to the journal's needs.

Running Costs

Running a journal involves continuous financial commitments to ensure smooth operations and high-quality publishing standards.

- **Personnel Efforts** – Editorial management, peer review coordination, technical support, and administrative work. See [Institutional publishing services: Service Team and Human Resources](#)
- **Hosting and Maintenance** – Platform hosting costs and ongoing technical support (e.g. updates).
- **Production Costs** – Formatting, copyediting, and typesetting of articles.
- **Persistent Identifiers** – Costs associated with assigning DOIs and other PIDs (e.g., Crossref fees).
- **Journal-Specific Requirements** – Any additional tools or systems needed for specialised publishing workflows.

Summary

Launching and sustaining a journal requires a clear funding model and careful budgeting to cover both the initial setup and ongoing operational costs, including planning, infrastructure, design, staffing, maintenance, and production services.

Checklist

- Define a sustainable business model (APC, diamond, or other).
- Provide guidance or resources for funding strategies if needed.
- Plan initial consulting and legal support for workflows and indexing.
- Budget for hardware and Information Technology (IT) infrastructure (servers, backups).
- Estimate setup costs for platform customisation and configuration.
- Design website, templates, and layouts according to branding and usability standards.
- Assess need for custom plugins or features.
- Allocate resources for personnel (editorial management, peer review, technical and administrative tasks).
- Include hosting and maintenance costs for the publishing platform.
- Cover production expenses (formatting, copyediting, typesetting).
- Budget for persistent identifiers (DOIs, Crossref fees).
- Consider any additional tools or systems required for specialised workflows.

Additional resources

- ❖ DIAMAS - ToolSuite – Funding:
<https://toolsuite.diamas.org/funding> (European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH))
- ❖ OA Network - Business Models for Journals:
<https://open-access.network/en/information/financing/business-models-for-journals>
- ❖ SPARC - Alternative Publishing Models to Support OA:
<https://sparcopen.org/our-work/alternative-publishing-models>

✓ IDENTIFIERS

Identifiers are essential in scholarly publishing. Understanding and implementing these identifiers correctly strengthens the journal's visibility, credibility, and interoperability in the scholarly ecosystem. This section covers key identifiers such as URLs for journal and article access, DOIs for permanent linking, ORCID for author identification, and ROR for institutional affiliation tracking.

Article identifiers

Article identifiers are essential for ensuring that digital content remains findable, accessible, and citable over time. They provide stable, persistent links to scholarly works and support long-term discovery, interoperability, and metadata integrity. This section outlines key types of identifiers and offers guidance on their effective use in journal publishing.

URL

[URLs](#) provide a stable and accessible way for readers, search engines, and indexing services to locate and reference journal content. A good URL improves discoverability, enhances search engine rankings (SEO), and ensures long-term access.

Recommendations

- Use human-readable URLs that reflect the content.
- Keep URLs short and follow a logical, standardised structure across the journal platform.
- A good URL improves discoverability, enhances search engine rankings (SEO), and ensures long-term access. Incorporate relevant keywords while avoiding unnecessary parameters and special characters.
- Always use HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) to ensure data security.
- Once published, URLs should remain unchanged. If a change is unavoidable, set up proper redirects to avoid broken links.
- Use lowercase letters to prevent inconsistencies in access across different systems.

URLs are defined by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) through its standards, while their management and domain name assignment is the responsibility of Internet Corporation for Assigned Names and Numbers (ICANN), which delegates this task to accredited registrars.

Persistent URL (PURL)

[PURLs](#) are intended to make up for the shortcomings of conventional URLs. Namely, resources changing name or location over time can break down, leading to URLs becoming unusable. This is often referred to as “link rot”.

A PURL is a type of URL designed to provide a stable link to a digital resource, even if its location changes. Unlike conventional URLs, PURLs redirect users to the updated location.

Developed by the nonprofit organisation [Online Computer Library Center](#) (OCLC) to help manage the long-term accessibility of digital resources (and now managed by Internet Archive), PURLs are not a formal International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) or World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) standard, but they are widely used on the Web.

Handles

[Handles](#) are another unique and persistent identification system for digital resources, such as documents, images or Internet services. They work as a standard protocol that allows resources to be accessed in a stable manner, even if their physical location changes. The [Handle System](#) is managed and defined by the [DONA Corporation](#) (Digital Object Numbering Authority), a non-profit organisation that oversees its global implementation and use. Although the system itself is free of charge, costs associated with its registration and maintenance may apply depending on the provider or institution using it.

Although both handles and PURLs (Persistent Uniform Resource Locators) are systems for persistent identification of digital resources, they have important differences. PURLs depend on DNS for resolution, which can affect their functionality if the domain changes. In contrast, handles do not depend on DNS, which gives them flexibility and persistence. In addition, handles can handle large volumes of identifiers and advanced functionality such as metadata and multiple resolutions, making them more suitable for long-term, large-scale applications.

It's important to clarify that the word "handle" is a generic term used within the Digital Object Architecture to refer to an identifier. The more formal term is DOI, or "digital object identifier." In the late 1990s, a group of publishers established the International DOI Foundation (IDF), which branded their implementation of handles as DOIs and added new features to create what is now known as the DOI System. DOI is a trademark of the IDF. In short, all DOIs are handles, but not all handles are DOIs.

Digital Object Identifier (DOI)

A [DOI](#) is a specific implementation of the Handle System used to assign unique, persistent identifiers to digital content. DOIs are managed by the IDF and follow standard syntax, metadata requirements, and registration procedures developed for scholarly and professional use. DOIs also boast wide adoption and infrastructure for citation and interoperability, making them the preferred choice for referencing scholarly publications.

The IDF delegates DOI registration to agencies such as DataCite and CrossRef, which charge membership and per-DOI fees. Publishers or platforms must join one of these agencies to register and maintain DOIs.

DOIs can be assigned to various objects depending on the service used:

- Journal DOI: Identifies the journal as a whole.
- Issue DOI: Applied to a specific journal issue.
- Article DOI: The most common use, unique identifier of an article.
- Other: Translations, datasets, and additional files can also receive DOIs.

Recommendations

- DOIs are not meant to be human-readable (but they can be).
- Once registered, DOIs should never be deleted or reused.
- Make sure journals define clear and unique DOI structure based on information that is readily available for all articles (ie., 10.xxxx/journalName.articleId).
- Encourage journals to use DOIs in article citations.
- Ensure Metadata Updates: Keep DOI records updated with correct metadata and URLs.

Researcher identifiers

ORCID

An [ORCID](#) is a persistent identifier assigned to researchers. ORCID distinguishes researchers with similar names, ensuring recognition of authorship in different databases and indexes. Many funders, publishers, and indexing services require the use of ORCIDs for author identification.

In addition to their role in identifying authors, ORCIDs can also be used for user authentication. Platforms can enable ORCID login via OAuth, allowing researchers to sign in using their ORCID credentials. This supports consistent identity management and facilitates linking user accounts with verified researcher profiles.

Metadata can be deposited to the ORCID database using the free Application Programming Interface (API). Access to the Member API, which offers advanced features such as writing data to ORCID records and retrieving trusted user information, requires a paid membership.

Recommendations

- Advise journals to use ORCID for all submitting authors.
- Recommend the use of authenticated ORCIDs by integrating the ORCID API with your platform over manual entry.
- Encourage journals to collect ORCIDs for peer reviewers to track review activities.
- Display authors' ORCIDs in article metadata, author profiles, and published articles.
- Consider becoming a member of ORCID for extended features.

Other Researcher Identifiers

While ORCID is the most widely adopted researcher identifier, other systems are also in use. For example:

- **ResearcherID** (managed by Clarivate) integrates with Web of Science and is often used in citation analysis.
- **Scopus Author ID** (managed by Elsevier) is automatically assigned to authors indexed in Scopus.
- International Standard Name Identifier (**ISNI**) is a broader identifier used across various sectors, including publishing, libraries, and music.

These identifiers are typically managed by specific platforms and serve complementary roles in disambiguating researcher identities, tracking publications, and integrating with bibliometric tools. However, ORCID remains the most interoperable and open system, particularly suited for OA publishing environments.

Organisation identifiers

ROR

A [ROR](#) ID is a persistent identifier assigned to research institutions, ensuring tracking of affiliations across databases and indexes. ROR helps disambiguate institutions with similar names and enhances the discoverability of research. Platforms can integrate ROR into their systems via the open API without any cost.

Recommendations

- Encourage journals to collect RORs for institutional affiliations in author metadata.
- Do not allow entering institution names manually and instead integrate RORs to your platform.
- Display RORs in article metadata and author affiliation sections.

Other Organisation Identifiers

In addition to ROR, other organisation identifiers are used across scholarly and publishing systems to uniquely identify institutions. These include:

- **ISNI**. An ISO-certified identifier that covers a wide range of organisations.
- **Ringgold IDs**. Proprietary identifiers used primarily by commercial publishers and subscription services to manage institutional access and author affiliations.

Summary

Persistent identifiers are key to ensuring the visibility and accessibility of journal content. As a platform manager, ensure that journals can use URLs for stable access, DOIs for permanent citation links, ORCIDs for author identification, and RORs for institutional tracking. Support consistent implementation, metadata updates, and seamless integration to enhance discoverability and interoperability across the scholarly ecosystem.

Checklist

DOIs

- Select a service provider for DOIs (for example Crossref or DataCite)
- Define a consistent DOI structure (e.g., 10.xxxx/journalName.articleID).
- Assign DOIs to all published articles, and optionally to issues and journals.
- Display DOIs on article landing pages, in citation formats, article metadata exports and any other output format.
- Ensure DOI metadata is updated when article details or URLs change.

ORCIDs

- Consider ORCID membership
- Require ORCID for all submitting authors.
- Do not allow free-text entry for ORCIDs - always use validated ORCID entries.
- Implement ORCID OAuth for authenticated collection.
- Allow ORCID login for user authentication.
- Allow to push publication data to author ORCID records.
- Display authors' ORCID IDs with standard icon and profile link.
- Include ORCIDs in article metadata exports.

RORs

- Use ROR IDs to identify institutional affiliations in author metadata.
- Integrate the ROR API to provide institution lookup/autocomplete.
- Do not allow free-text entry for affiliations - always use validated ROR entries.
- Include ROR IDs in article metadata exports.

Additional resources

- ❖ DataCite documentation:
<https://support.datacite.org/>
- ❖ Crossref documentation:
<https://www.crossref.org/documentation/>
- ❖ ORCID integration best practices:
<https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-best-practices/>

- ❖ ROR Documentation:
<https://ror.readme.io/>

✓ POLICIES & RIGHTS

Publishing and Rights policies are key elements in ensuring compliance with the principles of Open Science, transparency in publishing processes, and the proper management of published content. [DIAMAS \(now EDCH\)](#) has established a series of relevant recommendations that must be analysed and adapted to the needs of your service.

These guidelines not only establish good editorial practices, but are also requirements for indexing in directories such as [DOAJ](#) or the [Diamond Discovery Hub](#) (DDH), compliance with regional, institutional, or funder mandates, and integration into open infrastructures.

Their technical implementation in journal publishing platforms involves tasks like configuring licenses, creating static information pages, activating specific plugins, adding elements to the submission checklist, and defining editorial workflows that reflect these policies in a consistent and visible manner for authors, reviewers, and readers.

Below, we briefly list the [EDCH Toolsuite](#)'s best practices to suggest how they can be implemented and provide examples. Please visit the EDCH Toolsuite for additional details.

Requirement	Action
<p>Open license (articles and metadata)</p>	<p>Set the default license of your platform (e.g. Creative Commons Attribution license (CC BY)) and include this license in all publication formats (Portable Document Format (PDF), HyperText Markup Language (HTML), Electronic Publication (ePub), Journal Article Tag Suite (JATS), Text Encoding Initiative (TEI)) to ensure consistent visibility and reuse permissions across your content. The platform will display this information automatically on article landing pages and in metadata (e.g. via Open Archives Initiative (OAI)).</p> <p>Define a license for your metadata (e.g. CC0 license) and make it public through a static page in your publishing platform. A short statement such as “The metadata of the contents of this journal are offered under a CC0 license” is sufficient. Ensure that license icons or text are visible for both content and metadata to guarantee human- and machine-readable access.</p> <p>See EDCH: Use of open licences in open access publishing</p>

<p>Authors' Rights & Licensing</p>	<p>Authors' Rights Page: Create a static "Authors' Rights and Licensing" page stating that authors retain full copyright over their work and only grant the publisher a non-exclusive license to publish and distribute it under the selected open license (e.g., CC BY). Include an item in the submission checklist confirming that authors have read, understood, and accepted these terms before submission.</p> <p>Licensing and Derivatives: Clearly articulate in the "About" or "Publication Policy" sections the rights retained by authors, the license applied to the work, and the terms governing derivative works. Integrate this information into submission agreements and ensure it is visible on article landing pages and in metadata.</p> <p>See EDCH: Copyright, authors' rights policy.</p>
<p>Third-party copyright</p>	<p>Include a new item in the submission form checklist where authors declare that they have obtained permissions for any third-party material. Reflect this obligation in the author guidelines. Note that third-party material may remain under separate intellectual property rights and is not automatically covered by the license applied to the authors' article.</p> <p>See EDCH: Copyright, authors' rights policy.</p>
<p>User rights</p>	<p>Display a "User Rights" section or footer text per article, explaining reuse, distribution, and citation rights under the chosen license. Ensure license icons are prominently displayed. Creative Commons licenses are recommended.</p> <p>See EDCH: Use of open licenses in open access publishing</p>
<p>Transparency on rights retention</p>	<p>Provide a stable "Copyright & Licensing" page summarising licence, rights policy, self-archiving permissions, ownership, and policies on third-party material. Register rights policy on Sherpa Romeo and DOAJ.</p> <p>See EDCH: Diamond OA policies</p>
<p>Publication policy</p>	<p>Publish a stable "Publication Policy" page that clearly outlines procedure related to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Editorial procedures and workflows. ➤ Versioning and archiving of article versions. ➤ DOI assignment and citation practices. ➤ Journal ownership changes. <p>These statements could be integrated into the "About the Journal" section and editorial workflow templates of your Journal Management</p>

	<p>System (JMS), ensuring transparency and trust for authors, reviewers, and readers.</p> <p>See EDCH: Diamond OA policies</p>
<p>Ownership & changes in ownership</p>	<p>Use the “About” page to clearly identify:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The legal entity owning the journal (e.g., university, library) ➤ The governance model of the journal ➤ Procedures to transfer ownership or close the journal <p>Ensure this information is publicly accessible and regularly updated, providing transparency and trust for authors, reviewers, and readers.</p> <p>See EDCH: Ownership and governance</p>
<p>Self-archiving policy & preprints</p>	<p>Enable metadata fields for self-archiving, including preprints, Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM), or Version of Record (VoR). Publish a static page summarising the permitted versions and any embargo periods, ensuring compliance with Sherpa Romeo settings to align with funder and institutional policies.</p> <p>In the “Submission Guidelines”, clearly indicate whether preprints are accepted and ensure that relevant metadata fields for preprints are included in the submission form. Optionally, integrate with preprint servers via plugins or provide clear instructions for authors to deposit their preprints.</p> <p>See EDCH: Self-archiving policy guidance / Preprints</p>
<p>Research data & software</p>	<p>Add metadata fields for data and software DOIs to ensure proper citation and discoverability. Use a Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit (SWORD) plugin or manual deposit workflows for submission and archiving.</p> <p>Publish a “Data and Software Availability” statement for each article, clearly describing how readers can access the underlying datasets and software. For software, consider providing persistent identifiers such as Software Heritage Identifiers (SWHIDs) to ensure long-term traceability and reproducibility. More information on SWHIDs can be found at Software Heritage</p> <p>See EDCH: Research data sharing policy</p>

<p>Publication of negative results</p>	<p>Create a dedicated section (e.g., “Negative Results”) and update the Focus & Scope page to indicate the journal’s editorial willingness to consider such manuscripts. This practice promotes transparency, reproducibility, and reduces publication bias.</p> <p>See EDCH: Open Science practices</p>
<p>Peer review transparency</p>	<p>Clearly display the peer review model in the journal settings (e.g., single-anonymised, double-anonymised, open). If desired and possible, activate an open peer review plugin, or provide the review criteria in the “About” page.</p> <p>Making the peer review process transparent enhances trust and accountability for authors, reviewers, and readers.</p> <p>See EDCH: Editorial quality</p>
<p>EDIB (Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, Belonging)</p>	<p>Publish a stable “EDIB Policy” page in the About section, outlining the journal’s commitment to equity, diversity, inclusion, and belonging. Include optional demographic fields in register/submission forms to collect information about authors and reviewers, and monitor reviewer selection and editorial processes to ensure fair and inclusive practices.</p> <p>Take concrete actions to promote EDIB, such as setting diversity goals, tracking progress, supporting multilingualism, creating accessible content, and addressing potential discrimination, adopting a holistic approach that values and respects all identities and perspectives.</p> <p>See DIAMAS: Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB)</p>
<p>AI policy</p>	<p>Include a subsection in “Publication Ethics” explaining the permitted and prohibited uses of AI tools in writing, editing, or reviewing manuscripts, and specify transparency requirements for authors and reviewers.</p> <p>Although there are not yet standardised AI guidelines, emphasise the responsible use of AI as part of broader open science practices, including transparency, reproducibility, and accountability.</p> <p>See EDCH: Open Science practices</p>

Table 1: Policies & rights, and their implementation.

If your JMS allows it, install the [Discoverability Companion \(DISCO\) plugin](#) to better align your service with the principles of Diamond Journals. We also recommend completing the [DIAMAS](#)

[self-assessment](#) questionnaire, which provides a comprehensive and relevant evaluation of your compliance with these principles in the context of open science.

Summary

Publishing and rights policies are essential to comply with Open Science principles and ensure transparency and proper editorial management. DIAMAS and EDCH provide recommendations that should be adapted to each service and are key for meeting mandates and indexing in directories. Their technical implementation in journal management platforms involves configuring licenses, creating information pages, activating plugins, and adjusting editorial workflows.

Checklist

- **Open license (articles & metadata):** Define default content license (e.g., CC BY) and metadata license (e.g., CC0); publish on platform and galleys.
- **Authors' rights & licensing:** Create a static page on retained rights and applied licenses; include a submission checklist item confirming author acceptance.
- **Third-party copyright:** Include a checklist item for permissions on third-party material; reflect in author guidelines.
- **User rights:** Provide article-level footer or page explaining reuse rights under the chosen license; display icons.
- **Transparency on rights retention:** Static page summarising licenses, rights, self-archiving, ownership, and third-party material; register in Sherpa Romeo, DOAJ, DDH).
- **Publication policy:** Create a static page outlining editorial workflows, versioning, DOI assignment, and ownership change policies.
- **Ownership & changes in ownership:** Indicate legal entity, governance model, and transfer/closure procedures on 'About' page.
- **Self-archiving & Preprints:** Enable metadata fields (preprint, AAM, VoR); publish permitted versions and embargoes; accept preprints and include metadata fields.
- **Research data & software:** Add DOIs for data/software; use SWORD plugin or manual deposit; include a per-article availability statement (consider SWHID for software).
- **Publication of negative results:** Dedicated section; update Focus & Scope page.
- **Peer review transparency:** Display review model in settings/About page; optionally enable open review.
- **EDIB:** Publish EDIB policy; optional demographic fields in submissions; monitor reviewer selection and editorial processes.
- **AI policy:** Include section in 'Publication Ethics' explaining permitted and prohibited AI uses and transparency requirements.

Additional resources

- ❖ cOAlition S:
<https://www.coalition-s.org/>
- ❖ Creative Commons Licenses and Tools:
<https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/>
- ❖ DDH:
<https://ddh.diamas.org>
- ❖ DOAJ:
<https://doaj.org/>
- ❖ EDCH:
<https://diamas.org>
- ❖ Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) intellectual property:
<https://publicationethics.org/news-opinion/intellectual-property>
- ❖ DOAS self-assessment tool:
<https://diamas.fecyt.es/>
- ❖ CRAFT-OA - DISCO plugin:
<https://github.com/munipress/disco>

✓ CHOOSING A PLATFORM

Common Content Management System or Dedicated Journal Management System?

When choosing between a common Content Management System (CMS) like WordPress and a dedicated JMS like OJS, it's important to align your choice with the needs of your journal. Consider, at least, the following arguments.

Arguments for using a dedicated JMS

- You need a ready-to-use platform for the journals without much configuration.
- You need dedicated workflows for submissions, peer review, and publishing.
- Compliance with standards like OAI, DOAS, DOIs, and/or ORCID is critically important.
- Interoperability with repositories, indexing services, and citation tools is essential to ensure broad visibility and smooth integration.
- Scalability for multiple journals or high-volume submissions is important.
- You need journal-specific features extended with plugins.

Arguments for using a common CMS:

- You need a simple and flexible platform and have resources to build a journal layout.
- General functionality is enough, and journal-specific workflows aren't essential.
- Compliance with publishing standards is not a priority or can be handled manually.
- You don't need journal-specific features, nor expect to in the future.

Recommendation

A dedicated JMS is the best choice for a journal. It provides structured workflows for submissions and peer review, ensures compliance with academic standards, and scales effectively for multiple journals or high-volume submissions.

Proprietary or Free Open Source JMS?

When deciding between a proprietary system or FOSS solution, your choice will depend on your journal's resources, goals, ethics, and technical needs.

Arguments for using a Proprietary Software:

- Some proprietary platforms can include more features and services than FOSS
- You need a fully supported, ready-to-use platform with minimal setup effort.
- You have enough financial resources available for licensing fees and ongoing support.
- You prefer a single point of contact for troubleshooting and maintenance.

Arguments for using a Free Software:

- You want data sovereignty, avoid vendor lock-in, or retain organisational know-how.
- You value flexibility for customising workflows, design, and features.
- You want to optimise your long-term budget and avoid licensing fees.
- You have access to technical expertise or IT support for installation and updates.
- Community-driven development and transparency are important to you.

Recommendation

A Free Open Source JMS is the recommended choice. It offers flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and allows customisation to fit specific journal needs without licensing fees. With community-driven development and support, it ensures adaptability and long-term sustainability while aligning with open-access ethics and academic collaboration.

Self-Hosting a Free Open Source JMS vs. Using a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) Solution

When choosing between self-hosting a FOSS JMS and using a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) solution, consider how much control, technical resources, and ongoing support your journal needs.

- **Self-hosting** means you install and maintain the software on your own servers, giving you full control over customisation, data, and system settings. This option requires technical expertise for setup, updates, and troubleshooting.
- **SaaS (Software-as-a-Service)** refers to using a cloud-based solution where the service provider handles installation, updates, and maintenance. This option offers convenience and support, but less control over customisation and system management.

Arguments for choosing Self-Hosting:

- You need full control over customisation, updates, and system configurations.
- Your journal operates on a limited budget.
- You have the know-how to support editorial and publishing workflows.
- You have access to technical expertise or IT support.
- You prefer to manage your own hosting environment.
- You prefer to have control over data security and data privacy
- Community support is enough for you.

Arguments for choosing a SaaS Solution:

- You need a fully supported, ready-to-use platform with minimal setup effort.
- You have enough financial resources available for recurring fees.
- You require assistance and support with the editorial and publishing workflows.
- You want to avoid managing servers, updates, and data security.
- You prefer a single point of contact for troubleshooting and maintenance.

Recommendation

Self-hosting an open-source platform is the best choice. It provides full control over customisation, updates, and data security while avoiding recurring fees. With the right technical expertise or IT support, self-hosting ensures a cost-effective and sustainable solution, making it ideal for journals that prioritise flexibility and long-term independence.

Choosing between available Free Open Source JMS

There are several open-source software solutions available for managing and publishing academic journals. Each offers different features, levels of technical complexity, and approaches depending on editorial needs. The following section introduces three of the most prominent options.

OJS

OJS is a widely used open-source journal management and publishing platform designed to streamline the editorial workflow for scholarly journals. Developed by the PKP, OJS provides a comprehensive suite of tools for manuscript submission, peer review, editorial management, and online publishing.

Key advantages of OJS include its compliance with industry standards, cost-effectiveness, and strong community support. The platform supports multiple journals, multilingual interfaces, and various publishing models, making it a suitable choice for institutions, academic societies, and independent publishers. OJS is highly customisable, with a range of plugins and integrations to enhance functionality.

OJS is built using Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP) and MySQL (or PostgreSQL) and runs on a LAMP (Linux, Apache, MySQL/MariaDB, PHP) or WAMP (Windows, Apache, MySQL/MariaDB, PHP) stack. It requires a web server environment and can be hosted on institutional servers or through different hosting services. Its plugin architecture allows for easy customisation and integration with external publishing tools.

Read more: <https://pkp.sfu.ca/software/ojs/>

Janeway

Janeway is an open-source journal management and publishing platform developed by the Open Library of Humanities (OLH). Designed with a modern, modular architecture, Janeway supports the entire scholarly publishing workflow from submission and peer review to production, publication, and archiving.

Key advantages of Janeway include its focus on open infrastructure, streamlined editorial interface, and strong support for OA publishing. It offers features such as customisable submission forms, integrated eXtensible Markup Language (XML) production workflows, and

support for persistent identifiers like DOIs, ORCIDs, and RORs. Janeway is especially well-suited for publishers seeking a transparent, non-commercial alternative.

Built with Python and Django, Janeway uses PostgreSQL as its database and is typically deployed in a Linux environment. It supports integration with external systems via APIs and includes automated tools for metadata export, indexing, and preservation.

Read more: <https://janeway.systems/>

Lodel

L'Officiel D'édition Électronique (Lodel) is an open-source CMS developed for electronic publishing in the academic world, particularly in the humanities and social sciences. Created in 2000 by the French organisation Centre for Open Electronic Publishing (CLEO), it was designed to meet the specific needs of scholarly journals and books publishing, managing structured content, citations, multilingual texts, and peer-reviewed articles. It is widely used by French-speaking academic communities.

The software is developed by OpenEdition (formerly CLEO) and supports three: OpenEdition Journals (+600 journals), OpenEdition Books (+15000 Books), Calenda (+59000 events) of its four platforms. A major refactoring of Lodel is underway with the development of version 2.0. Since this version is not yet publicly available (as of October 2025), an annex — '*ANNEX: LODEL 2.0 PRELIMINARY INSTALL TOOLKIT*' — has been added to this document."

Read more (in French): <https://lodel.hypotheses.org/>

Summary

When you need to decide which platform to use for building a journal publishing service, you should consider several criteria, such as whether to choose a general-purpose CMS or one specifically designed for journals (JMS). You should weigh the pros and cons of proprietary software versus free and open-source alternatives, and also decide whether you prefer to host the system yourself or use a SaaS solution. Finally, in line with open science principles, we suggest reviewing some of the main free and open-source options available, such as OJS, Janeway, and Lodel.

Checklist

- Reflect on “Choosing Between a Common CMS and a Dedicated JMS”
 - Do you need built-in workflows for submissions, peer review, and publishing?
 - Is compliance with academic standards (OAI, DOIs, ORCID) essential?
 - Will you manage multiple journals or handle high submission volumes?
 - Do you prefer a plug-and-play solution with minimal configuration?
 - Or is a flexible general-purpose platform (e.g., WordPress) sufficient?

- Can you manually manage compliance and design workflows yourself?
- Reflect on “Proprietary vs. FOSS”
 - You want to ensure data sovereignty, are concerned about vendor lock-in, or aim to retain your organisation's know-how?
 - Do you need a fully supported, turnkey solution and can afford licensing fees?
 - Do you prefer full control, no licence costs, and customisation options?
 - Do you have internal IT support for setup, updates, and maintenance?
 - Is open development, transparency, and ethics a factor in your decision?
- Reflect on “Self-Hosting vs. SaaS”:
 - Do you want full control over data, customisation, and hosting environment?
 - Can your team manage technical maintenance and support workflows?
 - Would you rather delegate hosting, updates, and security to a provider?
 - Is your budget able to cover recurring SaaS service fees?
 - Do you prefer a single contact point for support and troubleshooting?

Additional resources

- ❖ DIAMAS Toolsuite: Choosing a Platform:
<https://toolsuite.diamas.org/choosing-platform-0>
- ❖ New university press toolkit: Choosing a Platform:
<https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/new-university-press-toolkit>
- ❖ Report on challenges and help measures faced by OA journals and platforms:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10496594>
- ❖ Analysis of the requirements for the Open Source infrastructure of the Open Research Europe Publishing Platform:
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/13928>
- ❖ OPERAS Special Interest Group (SIG) on Tools for Open Scholarly Communication:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5654319>

4 OJS

For the remainder of this document, **the focus will be on OJS**. The following sections will describe its main components, installation options, and operational considerations. Information regarding Lodel and its specific implementation details will be included in the annex.

✓ HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

In general, it is difficult to define precise hardware requirements for an application, as they largely depend on the type of service you intend to set up, how you configure it, and how successful it becomes.

In the case of OJS, the requirements depend primarily on your journal's characteristics. Individual journals that are larger, receive a higher number of concurrent visitors, or rely on complex infrastructures will naturally demand more hardware resources. To determine your own requirements, you can refer to estimations from other CMS platforms or feedback from community members. Keep in mind that hardware requirements will evolve as your journal grows and both data volume and concurrent traffic increase. Resource needs will also rise slightly if you use containerisation, and considerably much more if you opt for virtualisation.

For example, in a new magazine that primarily publishes text-based articles with some images, the entire workflow for each article (which includes several stages, with back-and-forth exchanges, peer review, and multiple galley proofs) will typically involve many Word, PDF, and JPG files. A rough estimate suggests that all files associated with a single article may occupy around 50 MB of storage.

If the journal publishes 50 articles per year, distributed across two issues, it will consume approximately 2.5 GB of disk space annually.

Of course, these figures can vary widely depending on the type of publication, the journal's history (including content stored outside the editorial workflow), and the number of articles published. Therefore, it is impossible to provide an exact estimate, but a rough reference for standard installations would be:

- For small journals: 1 Central Processing Unit (CPU) + 1GB ram + 10GB disk
- For regular journals: 2 CPU + 2GB ram + 30GB disk
- For big journals: 4 CPU + 4GB ram + 50GB disk
- For a full service (20 regular journals): 8 CPU + 16GB + 500GB disk

Summary

Hardware needs for OJS depend on journal size, expected traffic, and infrastructure complexity, and should be planned with scalability and possible containerisation or virtualisation in mind.

Specific hardware requirements depend on usage but 1 CPU with 1GB ram and 10GB of disk is enough to start and 4 CPU + 16GB + 500GB disk could hold a full service.

Checklist

- Estimate traffic, data volume, and infrastructure complexity.
- Plan for scalability to accommodate future growth.
- Increase resources if using containers or virtualisation.
- Use estimates from other CMSs or community experiences as a reference.

Additional resources

❖ PKP Forum

- Technical advices when number of journal increases in a single install of OJS3?:
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/technical-advice-when-number-of-journal-increases-in-a-single-install-of-ojs3/51194>
- Hardware requirements for more than 50 Journals:
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/hardware-requirements-for-more-than-50-journals/67898>

✓ HOSTING OPTIONS

When setting up OJS, users must first decide whether to install it on their own server (locally) or use an external OJS hosting provider. Each option has its own advantages and disadvantages, depending on the specific needs of the journal and the technical expertise of the administrators.

If you are just starting out or don't yet have a technical team to support the project, you will likely prefer to use an external hosting service. As your service grows, you may then want to take full control of your platform and move it on-premises.

OJS on your own server (on-premises)	
Advantages	Disadvantages
Full Control: Complete control over the server environment, configurations, and security settings.	Technical Expertise Required: Setting up and maintaining a server requires knowledge of operating systems, web servers, databases, PHP and OJS.
“Know-how” retention: Offers flexibility in innovation and decision-making. Avoids vendor lock-in.	Maintenance Responsibility: Updates, backups, and security patches must be managed by your IT team.
Data privacy: Full control over your data.	Support Responsibility: Your service will be responsible for providing support to editors and users.
Customisation: Easier to modify code, plugins, and themes according to specific requirements.	
No Hosting Fees: Avoids recurring costs associated with external hosting providers.	

Table 2: Additional resources.

OJS on External Hosting	
Advantages	Disadvantages
Ease of Setup: Hosting providers usually offer one-click installations or pre-configured environments.	Recurring Costs: External hosting requires ongoing subscription fees, which vary depending on the plan.
Scalability: External services usually offer an easy way to upgrade server resources as the journal grows in traffic and content.	Limited Customisation: Some hosting environments restrict access to server configurations, limiting deep customisation.
	Reliance on Third-Party Support: Troubleshooting server issues may require assistance from the hosting provider, which could lead to delays.

OJS on External Hosting	
	<p>Data privacy Allowing third-party users to access your data.</p>

Table 3: Installing OJS on External Hosting.

Summary

Choosing between local and external hosting for OJS depends on the journal's technical resources, budget, and long-term needs. Local installation is ideal for those who require full control on data, tools and customisation, while external hosting offers convenience, reliability, and ease of maintenance. Evaluating these factors will help determine the best approach for a successful OJS implementation.

Checklist

- Assess need for full control, deep customisation, and data privacy.
- Consider the budget for recurring hosting fees versus internal infrastructure costs.

If self-hosting:

- Evaluate internal technical expertise for installation and server management.
- Weigh responsibility for updates, backups, security and support.

If external-hosting:

- Check external hosting advantages such as easy setup, high availability, automated security, and scalability.
- Balance real costs, customisation limits, data privacy and dependency on third-party support when using.

✓ WHAT TECHNOLOGY SHOULD I USE FOR MY INFRASTRUCTURE?

OJS is an application developed on PHP, which is a scripting language that requires a web server, a database, and an operating system.

Usually OJS installations run on a LAMP stack although it is also possible to use it with nginx, postgresSQL or even Windows.

Although these are the essential software requirements to install OJS, you must keep in mind that applications are constantly changing (fixing bugs, adding new functionalities, etc.), so it is important to consider how you plan to maintain an up-to-date system.

There are several potential strategies for achieving this goal, 4 of which we will cover in this toolkit:

- **Manual:** The installation is done from the tarball distributed by PKP. Each new update involves downloading the new version and (carefully) overwriting the previous installation.
 - Pros: No great technical knowledge is required.
 - Cons: Maintenance can be challenging.
 - Recommended for: Testing and starting with OHS,
- **Git:** Installation is done via git, which allows for better version control.
 - Pros: Updates are easier to manage.
 - Cons: Good knowledge of git is a must.
 - Recommended for: Developers or IT teams who are already using Git in other projects. When following this strategy, it is advisable to use stable branches rather than the main development branch.
- **Virtualisation:** Installation is done on a virtual machine (proxmox, vagrant, vmware...) that includes the LAMP stack.
 - Pros: Virtual machines allow snapshots, which facilitates recovery in case of failures.
 - Cons: Virtualisation places a significant overhead on resource usage.
 - Recommended for: IT teams that have a lot of resources.
- **Containers:** Installation is done using containers (docker, podman, k8s...), which are much lighter than virtual machines and allow for an easier, standardised maintenance/upgrade process.
 - Pros: Preconfigured lightweight containers that include the entire LAMP stack. Easy upgrades with official images.
 - Cons: Requires basic knowledge of containers.
 - Recommended for: Experienced IT teams.

There is no right or wrong strategy. It all depends on the context in which it is applied.

The best strategy is the one that involves less time and effort during maintenance.

If you are just starting out, we suggest that you choose the strategy that is most familiar to your technical team. If your team already maintains other PHP applications, it is often a good idea to do it the same way and reuse previous knowledge. Over time, the team will become more experienced and will be able to alter their strategy accordingly.

Summary

OJS runs on a LAMP-type stack and can be installed manually, via git, in virtual machines, or in containers. The best strategy depends on the technical skills of the team; make sure your IT staff knows all options and let them decide.

Checklist

- Confirm the base stack (Linux/Apache/MySQL/PHP or equivalents).
- Plan how to keep the system updated over time.
- Ensure IT staff are familiar with all installation strategies and let them decide which one to use.

Additional resources

- ❖ PKP Docs - Administrator's Guide:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/admin-guide/en/>
- ❖ PKP Docs - Getting Started - System Requirements:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/admin-guide/en/getting-started#system-requirements>
- ❖ PKP Docs - How to Upgrade:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/dev/upgrade-guide/en/>
- ❖ Vagrant image (2020):
<https://github.com/pkp/vagrant>
- ❖ About Containers
 - PKP documentation about docker could be found in the official repository:
<https://github.com/pkp/containers>
 - Images for OJS and Open Monograph Press (OMP):
[DockerHub](#) / [PKP forum announcements](#)
 - Additional community tutorials and workshops
 - Meet the experts - Workshop #3: OJS Containerization (Docker)
 - Talk: <https://doi.org/10.5446/71656>
 - Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17494853>
 - OJS Containerization (Docker/Kubernetes):
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XI7vSygSqR8>

- PKP Dev Team: Setting up debugging:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qB6H0cl-NI8>
- Dojo: Ansible playbooks for a fully automated PKP server:
<https://github.com/marcbria/dojo>

✓ SINGLE OR MULTIPLE JOURNAL INSTALLATION?

OJS is the acronym of “Open Journal SystemS”. This plural comes from the fact that OJS is able to host multiple journals in a single installation. It means that if you plan to offer more than one journal, you will have to decide if you host a single OJS per journal or you host them all in a single installation.

This is called “tenancy” and, as one might expect, there are arguments in favor of both “single tenancy” (one independent OJS for each journal) and “multi-tenancy” (one installation for all your journals).

Figure 1: Multi-tenant and single-tenant OJS installations

There are several factors to take into consideration before choosing one model over another (resources, knowledge, time, functionalities, policies...), so the decision depend on your context, but this table tries to summarises the benefits of each approach:

Single-tenant	Multi-tenant
More flexibility: Easier to add / remove / change / upgrade only 1 journal.	Most commonly used: Better tested, easier to find help.
Independent upgrades: Faster & fewer issues.	Single upgrade: Less dispersion when upgrade.
Independent plugins: Journals with different needs.	Centralised administration: plugins and users management.
Independent instances: More resilient to failures/attacks.	Unification: “Portal” feature out of the box.
Isolated users: Smaller lists, better for privacy/GDPR.	Centralised users: They only register once.
Smaller Databases (DBs): Calls will be faster.	Searcher feature: Search includes all journals.
Less “downtime” when upgrading.	Easier to create new journals.
Segmented tracking/monitoring: Easier to detect the resources consumed by each journal.	Requires less knowledge and resources to start with.
Easier multi-domain setup: Certificates, redirections...	
Code customisation: Different theming or features.	

Table 4: Multi-tenant and single-tenant OJS installations benefits

If you are just starting, or want to avoid the overhead of managing multiple upgrades and building a custom journal portal, a **multi-tenant approach** is probably the best choice if you are satisfied with the multi-tenant features OJS provides “out of the box”.

On the other hand, if your journals differ in URLs, certificates, plugins, mailing systems, or other configurations, if you want to isolate users for better privacy, build your own independent “portal,” or improve performance and reduce downtime, you will likely prefer a **single-tenant approach**, managing each journal as an independent instance.

We would like to point out that, although there is no limitation to running OJS in a multi-tenant setup using containers, the **single-tenant setup is preferred** because it provides better isolation between journal instances.

Community projects such as **dojo** (see below) have been developed to streamline administration across instances and help manage multiple OJS installations.

Summary

OJS can host multiple journals either in a single installation (multi-tenant) or as separate installations per journal (single-tenant). Multi-tenant is simpler, with centralised management, built-in portal and search features, and easier upgrades—ideal for newcomers. Single-tenant provides greater flexibility, independent upgrades, better performance, and user isolation, but requires more resources and technical expertise.

Checklist

Reflect to decide between **single-tenant** or **multi-tenant**.

- Consider technical resources, maintenance capacity, and team expertise.
- Assess journal diversity: URLs, plugins, certificates, mailing systems, and privacy.
- Evaluate desired features: portal, centralised search, and user management.
- Factor in performance and expected downtime during upgrades.
- Explore community tools if managing multiple single-tenant installations.
- Match the tenancy model to the growth plan and operational context of your journals.

Additional resources

- ❖ PKP Docs - Administrator's guide - Multi-tenancy:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/admin-guide/en/deploy-multi-tenant>
- ❖ PKP Forum - Single vs Multi tenant BENEFITS lists:
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/hardware-requirements-for-more-than-50-journals/67898/9>
- ❖ Dojo: Ansible playbooks for a fully automated PKP server:
<https://github.com/marcbria/dojo>

✓ USER ROLES

Like all CMS, OJS includes user roles. Roles allow users to perform certain actions or access certain information. As in the physical world, a specific user can have one or many different roles in the journal (for example, they can be an editor, but also a layout designer).

The **Site Administrator** account is created as part of the installation process. There can only be one Site Administrator. The Site Administrator is responsible for: the overall OJS installation and Site Settings configuration, adding language files, creating any new journals on the installation, and ensuring the server settings are accurate. The Site Administrator handles periodic updates, usually in coordination with Journal Manager(s) and Editor(s).

The **Journal Manager** has access to all parts of the journal and is able to perform the following tasks: setting up the journal website; configuring system options; managing user accounts; enrolling Editors, Section Editors, Copyeditors, Layout Editors, Proofreaders, Authors, and Reviewers; creating new Sections for the journal; setting up Review Forms; editing email templates viewing statistics and reports; importing and exporting data, and accessing the editorial workflow and all journal submissions.

Note that the role of Journal Manager does not require advanced technical skills but rather filling in the data collected from the Editor and other respective persons/roles in the journal. The Journal Manager has access to all journal content and personal information about registered users, so they need to be 'a person of trust' with awareness of potential conflict if they decide to act as an author or reviewer in the journal.

The **Editor** has an overview of the entire review, editing and publishing process. The Editor shares documents and information with the Journal Manager, and is responsible for establishing the policies and procedures for the journal. Editors can manage accounts for authors, reviewers and add all other roles within the editing workflow: copyeditor, translator, etc.

The **Section Editor** is responsible for managing submissions assigned to a specific journal section (e.g., Research Articles, Reviews, Case Studies). Their role oversees the editorial workflow for manuscripts but usually does not include making final publication decisions (typically done by the Editor).

The **Author** can submit manuscript(s) to the journal directly through the journal's website. The Author is able to register to the platform, and is asked to provide metadata or indexing information. The Author can upload multiple files, in different forms: e.g. data sets, research instruments, or source texts. Type of the text can be chosen from the list provided in the system, or an Editor can update the list to suit the need of the Journal.

When logged in, the Author is able to track the submission through the review and editorial process. An Editor can communicate with the author(s) via the system where all communication

is tracked and recorded. The Author can participate in the copyediting and proofreading of submissions accepted for publication — if Editor(s) include them in the process via the system.

The **Reviewer** is selected by the Editor or Section Editor to review a submission. Reviewers can either be added to the system or create their own accounts and select the reviewer role. They may choose to join the reviewer pool for a specific journal or, if the platform hosts multiple journals (as in a multi-tenant OJS installation), for the entire platform. Journal Managers can also add the reviewer role to users already registered. The Reviewer is asked to submit reviews to the journal's website and are able to upload attachments for the use of the Editor and Author. The Reviewer can access the Reviewing form offered by the journal. Reviewers may be rated by Section Editors, if the rating system is implemented in the Journal. The Reviewer stays in the system and can access all the previous reviewing tasks.

The **Copyeditor** edits submissions to improve grammar and clarity, and depending on the journal's practice, works with editor(s) or section editor(s), or directly with authors to ensure everything is in place, ensures strict adherence to the journal's bibliographic and textual style, and produces a clean, edited copy for a **Layout Editor** or **Production Assistant** to turn into the galleys that will be in the published format of the journal. Copyeditors are often outsourced, and are not part of the permanent team and are added to the system by Editor or section Editor to submit copyedited and clean documents. Their work is done outside the platform and if outsourced, can produce extra costs for the journal. Some journals have an Editor or Section Editor assume this role.

The **Layout Editor** transforms the copyedited versions of the submission(s) into galleys in HTML, PDF, XML, or other file formats the journal has elected to use for online publication. A journal can have more than one galley. The Layout Editor can be outsourced and is added to the OJS by Editor or Section Editor, or doesn't have to have the account in OJS. The galleys can be obtained outside the system, and later submitted by the Editor or Section Editor or they can play the role(s) of Layout Editor as well. The Layout Editor role can be outsourced and added to OJS by the Editor or Section Editor. Alternatively, the person fulfilling this role may not need an OJS account at all, and can instead prepare galleys outside the system that are later uploaded by the Editor or Section Editor. This role may also be fully assumed by an Editor or Section Editor.

Note: At the time of writing, OJS is developing features to facilitate the conversion of documents into JATS/XML galley format. Therefore, the responsibilities of the Layout Editor related to galley creation may vary depending on the evolution of these tools. In any case, the Layout Editor must be able to generate galleys using external JATS-based workflows if required.

The **Proofreader** carefully reads over the galleys in the various formats the journal publishes (as does the author). The Proofreader (and the Author) record any typographic and formatting errors for the Layout Editor or Editor to fix.

Depending on the journal's policies, the Editor or Section Editor can also serve as Proofreader.

The **Reader** can create the account in the OJS in order to receive a notification email with the publication of each issue, which includes the Table of Contents for that particular issue.

Notes:

- It is not necessary to be a registered reader to access content and to read articles published in OJS.
- There are more roles that can be created within the journal, e.g. translator, designer... All potential roles can be created by the **Journal Manager** who can restrict the access of each role.
- The roles of Site Administrator, Journal Manager, Editors, Section Editors, Authors and Reviewers are all necessary within the system. All production roles (Copyeditor, Layout Editor, Proofreader, Translator, Designer, etc.) can be outsourced, with their work being done outside the system. The resulting drafts, galleys, or other files are later on uploaded in the designated place in the OJS system.

Summary

OJS uses a role-based system to manage access and responsibilities within a journal. Key roles include Site Administrator (overall system management), Journal Manager (journal setup and user management), Editors and Section Editors (policy, workflow, and manuscript oversight), Authors and Reviewers (content submission and evaluation), and production roles like Copyeditor, Layout Editor, and Proofreader. Additional roles (e.g., Translator, Designer) can be created as needed. Multiple roles can be granted to a single user depending on tasks and trust level.

Checklist

- Assign a **Site Administrator** for overall OJS installation and updates.
- Designate **Journal Managers** to configure journals, manage users, and coordinate workflow.
- Define **Editors** for policy, submission oversight, and decision-making.
- Assign **Section Editors** to manage specific journal sections.
- Enable **Authors** to submit and track manuscripts, and optionally participate in copyediting/proofreading.
- Select **Reviewers** and manage the review process, including forms and attachments.
- Include **Copyeditors** to ensure adherence to style and produce clean manuscripts.
- Assign **Layout Editors** to convert manuscripts to publication formats (HTML, PDF, XML).
- Include **Proofreaders** for final checks of galleys before publication.
- Allow **Readers** to register for notifications; content can remain publicly accessible.
- Consider additional roles (e.g., Translators, Designers) and restrict access as appropriate.

- Evaluate whether users may perform multiple roles based on skills, workload, and trust.

Additional resources

- ❖ Roles in OJS:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/learning-ojs/journal-managers/en/users#permissions-roles>

✓ INSTALLATION

This section explains how to manually install and configure OJS. Alternatively, you can use preconfigured OJS images available as containers or virtual machines, as outlined in [OJS: Upgrade](#).

To install OJS, you will need a web server (e.g., Apache or Nginx), a database (MySQL, MariaDB, or PostgreSQL), PHP, and a domain. If you have all the necessary requirements set up, you can proceed to download OJS from the official website, uncompress the files, and set up the folder permissions. Alternatively, you can use Git to clone the OJS repository if you prefer.

You can find the exact installation steps in the official OJS documentation, linked below. After completing this step, proceed to the OJS installation page to enter some basic configuration data like database parameters, create an administrator account, etc. The next step is to edit the `config.inc.php` file where the full OJS configuration is stored. It is essential to take the time to configure OJS correctly by thoroughly editing the `config.inc.php` file.

Pay close attention to configuring your mailer correctly, as improper configuration can cause issues with sending emails within OJS.

OJS handles email communications for notifications, user registrations, submission updates, editorial decisions, and more. Proper configuration is essential for reliable delivery, especially in multi-journal installations where multiple journals share the same OJS instance but may have distinct user bases, domains, or branding. Email setup is primarily managed in the `config.inc.php` file located in the root directory of your OJS installation. This file contains an `[email]` section where you define how emails are sent, including the sending method (PHP's built-in `mail()` function or Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP)), authentication, and envelope sender options.

Improper email configuration can result in delivery failures, spam filtering, or security issues, such as Sender Policy Framework (SPF), DomainKeys Identified Mail (DKIM), and Domain-based Message Authentication, Reporting, and Conformance (DMARC) violations. In multi-journal setups, these issues are magnified because emails from different journals may originate from distinct user addresses while sharing the same server. This guide explains the configuration process in detail, emphasising how to ensure the "From" address reflects the real user's email (e.g., the editor's or author's actual address) rather than a generic default address. Special attention is given to the roles of **`force_default_envelope_sender`** and **`default_envelope_sender`**, which are critical for achieving this while maintaining deliverability, particularly in multi-journal OJS instances.

Using PHP's mail() Function

- This method is the default if no other settings are specified.
- It relies on the server's local mail transfer agent (MTA), such as Sendmail or Postfix.
- Configuration: No specific settings are required in the [email] section, but the server must be configured to relay emails properly.
- Drawbacks: Limited authentication options, higher risk of spam classification, and potential restrictions in shared hosting environments.
- Best for: Simple, low-volume setups or testing

Using SMTP

- Enable by setting `smtp = On` in the [email] section.
- Key parameters:
 - `smtp_server = smtp.example.com`
(e.g., `smtp.gmail.com` for Gmail, `smtp.office365.com` for Microsoft 365).
 - `smtp_port = 587`
(common for Transport Layer Security (TLS): 465 for Secure Sockets Layer (SSL); 25 unencrypted - to be avoided for security).
 - `smtp_auth = tls`
(or `ssl`; enables authentication — supported mechanisms are SSL or TLS).
 - `smtp_username = yourusername@example.com`
(SMTP account username).
 - `smtp_password = yourpassword`
(SMTP account password — store securely. Avoid committing to version control).

Configuring the "From" Address to Use the Real User's Email

By default, OJS sets the "From" header (RFC 5322.From) to the email address of the user triggering the email, such as an editor's address for decision notifications or an author's for submission confirmations. This approach enhances personalisation and authenticity, as recipients see the email originating from a relevant individual (e.g., `editor@journaldomain.com`) rather than a generic address like `no-reply@ojsinstance.com`.

However, this can lead to deliverability issues:

- If the user's email domain (e.g., `university.edu`) differs from the sending server's domain (e.g., `yourhosting.com`), SPF checks may fail because the server is not authorised to send on behalf of that domain.
- The user's domain might reject the email if it does not align with its DMARC policies.
- In multi-tenant OJS instances (where multiple journals operate on one installation via `installed = On` and multi-context mode), users from different journals may have emails from various domains, increasing the risk of inconsistencies and spam flags.

To address these challenges while preserving the real user's email in the "From" address:

- Use **force_default_envelope_sender = On** combined with **default_envelope_sender**.
- This configuration separates the envelope sender (RFC 5321.MailFrom, also known as Return-Path) from the "From" header.

Key Settings: `force_default_envelope_sender` and `default_envelope_sender`

- **allow_envelope_sender = On:** Enables OJS to specify a custom envelope sender. This may not be supported by all servers (e.g., some hosts restrict it), so testing is necessary. Set to Off if the server does not support it.
- **default_envelope_sender = no-reply@yourdomain.com:** Specifies the default email address for the envelope sender. This should be an address controlled by the OJS installation's domain to ensure SPF/DKIM compliance.
- **force_default_envelope_sender = On:** Forces all emails to use the `default_envelope_sender` as the envelope sender, overriding any per-email attempts to set it differently.
 - **Functionality:** The envelope sender handles bounces and is checked by SPF. With this setting enabled, the envelope sender is always the controlled address (e.g., no-reply@yourdomain.com), while the "From" header remains the user's real address (e.g., editor@journalA.com). The "Reply-To" header is set to the user's address or the original "From" for replies.
 - **Importance:** This prevents delivery failures due to mismatched domains. Bounces are directed to the central `default_envelope_sender` address, simplifying monitoring in a multi-tenant setup where journals may not share admin access.
 - **Multi-Tenant Relevance:** This is critical in multi-tenant instances because each journal may potentially use different primary contacts and user domains. Without forcing the envelope sender, emails from Journal A's users might fail SPF checks if the server is not authorised for their domains, impacting all journals' reliability. A shared, controlled envelope sender ensures consistency while allowing journal-specific "From" addresses (configured per journal in Settings > Journal > Contact).
 - **Warnings:** When `force_default_envelope_sender = On`, editing the envelope sender per email has no effect—it is always set to the default. Ensure the domain in `default_envelope_sender` matches the OJS server's domain to avoid SPF issues.

Avoiding "From" Rewriting with DMARC Compliance

- If stricter DMARC compliance is needed (e.g., for users with external domains), the settings `force_dmarc_compliant_from = On` and `dmarc_compliant_from_displayname = "%n via %s"` (where `%n` is the user's name, `%s` is the site/journal name) can be used.
- These settings rewrite the "From" header to something like "User Name via Journal <no-reply@yourdomain.com>", moving the real user's address to "Reply-To".
- **Caution:** This approach changes the "From" to a default-like address, which conflicts with the goal of using the real user's address. Enable only if DMARC failures occur; otherwise, keep it Off to preserve the user's "From" address.
- In multi-journal setups, this may make emails appear more uniform but less personalised—user feedback should be tested.

Bounce Handling

- Bounces (undeliverable emails) are sent to the envelope sender.
- With `force_default_envelope_sender = On`, all bounces are directed to `default_envelope_sender`, simplifying management in multi-journal environments.
- OJS does not automatically process bounces, but bounces can be manually reviewed to update user emails in the system.

Security and Deliverability Tips

- **SSL/TLS:** Always use encrypted SMTP (tls/ssl) to protect credentials and data.
- **Rate Limiting:** Set `time_between_emails = 3600` and `max_recipients = 10` to avoid being flagged as spam.
- **Testing:** After configuration changes, restart the web server and test emails from different journals/users. Use OJS's "Send Test Email" feature (if available) or trigger notifications.
- **Multi-Tenant Considerations:** Configure journal-specific emails (e.g., the journal's contact email) in Settings > Journal > Contact. Ensure the global configuration supports varied "From" addresses without conflicts.
- **Common Pitfalls:** If emails fail to send, check server logs (e.g., Apache/Nginx error logs, PHP error logs). Verify that the domain in `default_envelope_sender` matches the OJS installation. For hosted environments like Office 365, update SPF/DKIM records.
- **Resources:** Consult the PKP Documentation (e.g., sections on email and configuration) for version-specific details. For OJS 3.x, these settings are consistent across releases.

This configuration ensures reliable and personalised email delivery, with the "From" address reflecting the real user's email while using a forced envelope sender for compatibility, which is especially crucial in multi-tenant OJS instances. If issues persist, consult the hosting provider or PKP forums for support.

OJS Security Notes

Securing an OJS installation is critical to protect sensitive data, prevent unauthorised access, and ensure operational reliability, particularly in multi-tenant environments. These general notes outline key strategies to enhance OJS security, focusing on server configuration, user management, and proactive monitoring to mitigate vulnerabilities and maintain system integrity.

- **Secure Server Environment:** Deploy OJS on a server with an updated operating system and web server (Apache/Nginx). Apply the latest security patches and disable unnecessary services or ports (e.g., close port 22 if Secure Shell (SSH) isn't needed). Use a firewall (e.g., ufw or firewalld) to restrict access to only required ports (80, 443). Enable HTTPS
- **Database Security:** Use a dedicated database user with minimal privileges (SELECT, INSERT, UPDATE, DELETE) and a strong password. Store credentials securely in config.inc.php. Regularly back up the database and test restoration processes to ensure recoverability. Consider encrypting the database connection with SSL if supported by the database server.
- **User Management:** Enforce strong passwords for all OJS accounts and implement two-factor authentication (2FA) via plugins if available. Regularly audit user accounts, removing inactive ones, especially in multi-tenant setups where users may belong to different journals. Assign roles (e.g., Editor, Reviewer) with minimal permissions and review them periodically to prevent privilege escalation.
- **Regular Updates and Patching:** Keep OJS, plugins, and server software up to date, prioritising patch-level upgrades as they address critical security vulnerabilities. Check OJS release notes and subscribe to the PKP Security Notifications mailing list for alerts. Test updates in a staging environment before applying to production
- **Monitoring and Logging:** Enable logging (enable_logging = On in config.inc.php) and regularly review OJS, web server, and PHP logs for suspicious activity (e.g., failed logins, unusual requests). Use tools like Fail2Ban to block brute-force attempts. Implement uptime and security monitoring to detect issues like traffic spikes or downtime promptly.
- **Additional Protections:** Disable risky PHP functions in php.ini (e.g., disable_functions = exec,shell_exec,system). Use a Web Application Firewall (WAF) like ModSecurity to filter malicious requests. Disable debug mode (debug = Off, show_stacktrace = Off) to avoid exposing sensitive information
- **Community and Documentation:** Leverage the PKP Documentation for detailed security guidelines and best practices. Engage with the PKP Community Forum to share solutions and seek advice on emerging threats or configurations. Stay informed about OJS-specific vulnerabilities through PKP's security advisories.

After completing the OJS configuration, you can visit the site to check if everything is working correctly. You can also use an OJS Docker image to install OJS by visiting the DockerHub image repository or GitHub.

Getting help

For assistance with OJS, the [PKP Community Forum](#) is a valuable resource where users can seek help, share solutions, and engage with the OJS community. This active platform includes discussions on troubleshooting, configuration, plugins, and best practices, with contributions from OJS administrators, developers, and PKP staff. Users can search existing threads for solutions, post specific questions, or browse categories like installation, upgrades, or multi-journal setups. Joining the forum and participating in discussions ensures access to timely, community-driven support and insights from experienced users.

The official OJS documentation, hosted at <https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/>, is a comprehensive resource provided by the Public Knowledge Project (PKP) for managing and troubleshooting OJS installations. It covers detailed guides on installation, configuration, upgrades, user management, and security best practices, tailored for administrators, editors, and developers. The documentation is regularly updated to reflect the latest OJS versions and includes specific sections for multi-journal setups, plugin management, and email configuration. Users can access step-by-step instructions, troubleshooting tips, and best practices, making it an essential starting point for resolving issues or optimising an OJS instance.

Summary

Manually installing OJS requires preparing a server environment, downloading or cloning the application, setting the appropriate file permissions, and completing the web-based installer with database and administrator details. The primary configuration is managed in *config.inc.php*, where correct mail settings are critical. Security hardening, logging, updates, and monitoring are also necessary to maintain a stable and compliant installation. Note that these steps are not required when using containers or virtual machines that provide a preconfigured environment.

Checklist

- Confirm server requirements (web server, PHP version, supported database, domain).
- Download or clone OJS source code and set correct directory permissions.
- Follow the official documentation for step-by-step installation.
- Run the installer and set database details and the admin account.
- Edit *config.inc.php* thoroughly, including general, file, and security settings.
 - Configure email in the [email] section (mail() or SMTP).
 - If using SMTP, define server, port, encryption, username, and password.
 - Set the envelop variables when required.
 - Verify SPF, DKIM, and DMARC alignment, especially in multi-journal setups.
 - Test email delivery and review logs for errors.
- Harden the server (HTTPS, firewall, remove unused services).
- Restrict database privileges and store credentials securely.

- Disable risky PHP functions and ensure debug mode is off.
- Enable logging and monitor OJS, web server, and PHP logs.
- Keep OJS, plugins, and server software updated.
- Validate the installation in the browser or use Docker if preferred.
- Consult PKP documentation and the PKP Community Forum for further support.

Additional resources

- ❖ PKP Docs - Administrator's Guide - Getting Started:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/admin-guide/en/getting-started>
- ❖ PKP Docs - Release Notebooks:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/dev/release-notebooks/>
- ❖ PKP Docs - Learning OJS for Site Administrators:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/learning-ojs/site-admin/en/>
- ❖ Meet the experts - Workshop #4 - Configuration options in OJS
 - Talk: <https://doi.org/10.5446/71699>
 - Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17251131>

✓ MAINTENANCE

As with any software, regular maintenance is essential to ensure that OJS operates smoothly, securely, and efficiently. Proper maintenance not only enhances performance but also protects the system from security vulnerabilities and data loss.

Regular Software Updates

Importance: Keeping OJS up to date is crucial for security and functionality. Updates often include patches for security vulnerabilities, performance improvements, and new features. Notably, patch-level upgrades (e.g., from 3.3.0-15 to 3.3.0-21) are both safe and critical, as they address specific security vulnerabilities without major system changes. Many recent attacks on OJS instances have occurred because IT teams neglected these minor but essential updates, leaving systems exposed to known exploits.

Steps:

- Check for Updates: Regularly visit the [PKP website](#) or the [OJS GitHub repository](#) for the latest releases and announcements.
- Review Release Notes: Consult the release notes for each update to understand changes, new features, and potential breaking changes that may affect your installation.
- Backup First: Always back up your database and files before applying updates to prevent data loss in case of issues during the upgrade process.
- Apply Updates: Follow the official [OJS upgrade documentation](#) to apply updates smoothly. Test the updated system in a staging environment before deploying to production.

Backup Strategies

Importance: Regular backups are vital to prevent data loss in case of hardware failure, hacking, or other unexpected events.

Steps:

- Automated Backups: Set up automated daily backups of both the database and the file system to ensure consistent data protection.
- Offsite Storage: Store backups in multiple locations, including secure offsite or cloud storage, to safeguard against physical damage, theft, or server failure.
- Test Restores: Periodically test backup restoration processes to verify that data can be recovered without issues, ensuring reliability in emergencies.

Security Practices

Importance: Protecting the journal's data from unauthorised access and breaches is critical to maintaining trust and system integrity.

Steps:

- **Secure Server:** Ensure the server hosting OJS is secured with an updated operating system, the latest security patches, and a properly configured firewall.
- **Strong Passwords:** Enforce strong, unique passwords for all user accounts and encourage the use of password managers.
- **SSL/TLS:** Implement SSL/TLS certificates to encrypt data transmitted between the server and users, ensuring secure communication.
- **Regular Audits:** Conduct regular security audits to identify and mitigate potential vulnerabilities, using tools recommended in the PKP documentation.

User Management

Importance: Proper management of user roles and permissions is crucial for maintaining system integrity and preventing unauthorised access.

Steps:

- **Role Assignment:** Clearly define and assign user roles (e.g., Editor, Reviewer, Author) to control access levels and limit permissions to what is necessary.
- **Regular Reviews:** Periodically review user accounts and roles to ensure they remain appropriate, removing inactive accounts or updating roles as needed.
- **Training:** Provide training and resources, such as the [PKP Documentation](#), to ensure users follow best practices and understand their responsibilities.

Plugin Management

Importance: Plugins extend the functionality of OJS but need to be managed carefully to maintain system stability and security.

Steps:

- **Compatibility Checks:** Before installing or updating plugins, verify their compatibility with your OJS version by consulting the plugin documentation or release notes on the PKP website.
- **Minimal Plugins:** Install only necessary plugins to reduce system complexity and minimize potential security risks.
- **Regular Updates:** Keep all installed plugins up to date

- Review Release Notes: Check the release notes for plugins to understand changes, bug fixes, or new dependencies before updating.

System Monitoring

Importance: Proactive monitoring ensures the early detection of performance issues, security threats, or system errors, allowing for timely resolution.

Steps:

- Performance Monitoring: Use server monitoring tools to track CPU, memory, and disk usage to ensure OJS runs efficiently, especially during high-traffic periods.
- Error Logs: Regularly review OJS and server error logs to identify and troubleshoot issues, such as failed login attempts or plugin errors
- Uptime Checks: Set up uptime monitoring to receive alerts if the OJS instance becomes unavailable, ensuring minimal downtime.
- Security Monitoring: Implement tools to detect suspicious activity, such as multiple failed login attempts or unexpected traffic spikes, and take corrective action promptly.

Summary

Regularly check the PKP website or GitHub for software updates, review release notes, back up data, test updates in a staging environment, and apply them following official documentation. Set up automated daily backups, store them offsite, and periodically test restores. Secure the server, enforce strong passwords, use SSL/TLS, conduct regular security audits, and subscribe to the PKP Security Mailing List for updates. Assign user roles, review accounts periodically, and train users with PKP Documentation. Verify plugin compatibility, use only necessary plugins, keep them updated, and check their release notes. Monitor system performance, review error logs, ensure uptime with alerts, and detect suspicious activity promptly.

Checklist

- Check the PKP website or OJS GitHub repository for the latest software releases and patch-level updates.
- Review release notes for software and plugin updates to understand changes and compatibility.
- Back up the database and file system before any updates or major changes.
- Test updates in a staging environment before deploying to production.
- Schedule and verify automated daily backups of the database and file system.
- Store backups in secure offsite or cloud storage and test restoration processes quarterly.
- Update the server operating system and apply security patches regularly.
- Enforce strong passwords and enable SSL/TLS for secure data transmission.

- Conduct security audits and subscribe to the PKP Security Mailing List for alerts.
- Review and update user roles and permissions, removing inactive accounts.
- Provide user training with PKP Documentation resources.
- Verify plugin compatibility and update plugins to the latest versions.
- Monitor server performance, review error logs, and set up uptime and security alerts.

Additional resources

- ❖ PKP Documentation:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/>
- ❖ Release Notes:
https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/ojs_download/
- ❖ PKP Security Mailing List:
<https://lists.publicknowledgeproject.org/lists/?p=subscribe&id=1>
- ❖ PKP Forum - Collaborative list of spam user patterns:
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/collaborative-list-of-spam-user-patterns/65190>
- ❖ Security plugins
 - BetterPassword plugin:
<https://github.com/ulsdevteam/pkp-betterPassword>
 - HoneyPot plugin:
<https://github.com/ulsdevteam/pkp-formHoneypot>

✓ UPGRADE

In some cases, updating OJS can be challenging for IT services. There can be multiple contributing factors (big software changes, DB issues, lack of experience with OJS upgrades, etc.) but one major issue is often the lack of ongoing technical attention to OJS installations. If an OJS instance is not regularly upgraded, a sudden large jump between versions is liable to result in unforeseen issues and difficulties with substantial changes.

Before upgrading, it is essential to understand the way PKP names its developments. Specifically, PKP uses semantic versioning, which is represented as a list of numbers such as 3.3.0-17. These numbers have names and meanings, and each describes the type of changes you can expect.

In order to understand the upgrade process, you should first determine the size of the upgrade “jump”. A jump from version 3.3.0-6 to 3.3.0-7 can likely be done with minimal downtime and it’s safe (are only patches that don’t include “breaking changes”). However, a jump from version 2.4 to 3.2 will be a long, complex process with a higher risk of introducing problems.

You should also bear in mind that not all upgrades can be performed directly. If the version gap is large, intermediate upgrades through earlier versions may be required. For example, when upgrading from 2.x to 3.3, you must first upgrade to 3.2.1-6.

It is also important to always perform upgrades in a test space and never to apply them without **first making a backup**.

Another important factor to take into account is your installation type. As mentioned in [OJS: What technology should I use for my infrastructure](#), OJS can be installed and managed using the following routes:

1. **Tarball:** Manual installation of the LAMP stack and then OJS from the releases packaged by PKP.
2. **Git:** Manual installation of the LAMP stack and then OJS using the git version manager.
3. **Containers:** Using PKP’s [official docker images](#) or your own.
4. **Virtual machines:** Using PKP’s [vagrant boxes](#) or your own.

Depending on your installation, the upgrade process may be more or less complex.

If you opt for route 1 (tarball)...

PKP offers a [detailed upgrade guide](#) in the PKP’s Documentation Hub.

If you opt for route 2 (git)...

Take in consideration that upgrading OJS via Git requires familiarity with version control workflows and the specific structure of OJS repositories. You will need to manually install the LAMP stack if not already done, and then manage OJS versions using Git commands.

Key resources include:

- PKP documentation - Check for any relevant README files in the Git repository, particularly those related to upgrading workflows.
- PKP Admin Guide Appendix 1: [Create a protected OJS 3 sandbox staged with Git](#) - provides step-by-step instructions for setting up a staging environment for testing upgrades.
- Community guide - [Running a production OJS site with Git for dummies \(like me\)](#)” by Antti-Jussi (TSV) - practical tips for managing OJS with Git in production environments.

It is recommended to always perform upgrades in a **sandbox or test environment** before applying changes to the live instance. Large version jumps may require intermediate steps or branch merges, so understanding the Git workflow is essential.

If you opt for route 3 (containers)...

Containerised installations (using Docker or similar technologies) provide a more isolated and reproducible environment, but upgrading requires knowledge of container management.

When using containers, ensure that persistent data volumes (for the database, uploaded files, and configuration) are correctly mapped and backed up before performing an upgrade. OJS introduce new variables in the config file, so double-check it to avoid issues during upgrade. If you create a volume for your plugins, notice those plugins should also be updated to the newest version, so the general recommendation is disabling the plugins-volume and let OJS upgrade with the plugins packaged in the image. Take in consideration that upgrades may involve updating both the OJS container image and any supporting services, such as databases or cache layers.

Additional resources about PKP containers could be found in [OJS: What technology should I use for my infrastructure](#).

If you opt for route 4 (virtual machines)...

Upgrading OJS installed in virtual machines is less documented and can vary significantly depending on the Virtual Machine (VM) setup. No public resources were found.

Finally, in all scenarios, you should also keep in mind that your upgrade will be different if your OJS installation is single-tenant (a single journal for each OJS) or multi-tenant (a single OJS for all your journals).

As discussed in the section [OJS: Single or multiple journal installation](#), a single-tenant installation allows for reduced “down time” (as each journal can be upgraded separately) and the ability to customise the upgrade experience for each journal, but it means multiple upgrades that (without automation tools) require more management time. On the other hand, a multi-tenant installation implies a single upgrade for your entire service, which may be easier to manage, but at the same time can be slower and more complex as it involves multiple journals.

It is generally advisable to run the upgrade script from the command line, ensuring that all error messages are visible and that sufficient memory is allocated to prevent the process from stopping mid-execution.

Before performing an upgrade, it is advisable to review the documentation for the target version. PKP publishes *release notebooks* in the [PKP Docs Hub](#) which provide technical and contextual information, and *release notes* in the official OJS GitHub repository (for example, [release-notes/README-3.5.0](#)), where changes and potential issues are detailed. Reviewing both resources helps plan the process and prevent errors.

Summary

Upgrading OJS requires careful planning, backups, and testing, especially for large version jumps. The process and the effort depend on your installation type (tarball, Git, containers, virtual machines) and whether you use single-tenant or multi-tenant setups. Smaller updates are straightforward, but major upgrades carry higher risks and require a staged approach.

Checklist

- Understand PKP **semantic versioning** to assess upgrade complexity.
- Determine the size of the **version jump**; larger jumps require more preparation.
- Always **back up** your system before upgrading.
- Test upgrades in a **staging environment** before applying to production.
- Consider your **installation type**: tarball, Git, containers, or virtual machines.
- Check if your OJS is **single-tenant** or **multi-tenant** to plan downtime and management effort.
- Review available **upgrade guides and community resources** for your installation route.
- Plan resources and time for handling **potential issues** during the upgrade.

Additional resources

- ❖ “OJS Releases” page will be published soon in PKP website:
<https://pkp.sfu.ca/software/ojs/releases>

- ❖ PKP Docs - How to Upgrade:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/dev/upgrade-guide/en/>
- ❖ PKP Docs - Upgrade OJS 2 to 3:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/upgrading-ojs-2-to-3/en/upgrading-ojs>
- ❖ PKP Docs - Release Notebooks:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/dev/release-notebooks/>
- ❖ OJS Release notes:
<https://github.com/pkp/ojs/blob/main/docs/release-notes/README-3.5.0>
- ❖ PKP Forum - Upgrade issues in PKP Forum:
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/search?q=upgrade>
- ❖ Create a Protected OJS 3 Sandbox:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/admin-guide/3.3/en/appendix-1.-create-a-protected-ojs-3-sandbox-staged-with-git>
- ❖ Meet the experts - Workshop #1 - OJS Upgrade
 - Talk: <https://doi.org/10.5446/71579>
 - Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17120752>

✓ PLUGINS

A plugin for OJS is a software add-on that enhances or extends the platform's functionality. These plugins can provide various features and integrations, improving the publishing process for journal managers, editors, reviewers, and authors. By installing and configuring plugins, OJS users can tailor their journal management and publishing system to better meet their specific needs and preferences.

Installing a plugin in OJS is typically done either via the OJS user interface (UI) or manually. Only a Site Administrator can install a new plugin.

There are two broad categories of plugins: site-wide plugins and journal-specific plugins. The former operates at the level of the entire OJS installation, and any changes made by these plugins affect the entire platform. The second operates at the level of individual journals, and their administrators can decide on the installation and configuration of these plugins.

Sometimes new plugins or plugins developed by users or contributors outside PKP will not appear in the Plugin Gallery and must be installed separately.

It is important to install only plugins that are compatible with the specific OJS version. Installing incompatible plugins can result in serious problems in the software. The live plugin gallery list on GitHub and the [PKP Plugins Compatibility list](#) can help check compatibility.

The CRAFT-OA project created a set of OJS Diamond Plugins aiming to increase the visibility of journals and make editors' work easier.

Here are examples of other popular OJS plugins along with brief descriptions:

- CrossRef XML Export Plugin – Supports the automatic registration of DOIs with CrossRef and the export of XML metadata in Crossref format for manual DOI deposits.
- QuickSubmit Plugin – allows editors to quickly submit and publish articles, bypassing the standard submission process.
- Usage Statistics Plugin – collects and displays detailed statistics about article views and downloads, helping editors monitor readership and journal reach.
- DOAJ Export Plugin – simplifies the process of indexing the journal in the DOAJ by easy export of journal metadata in a DOAJ-compliant format.

In addition to plugins that improve workflow and discoverability, OJS also provides several plugins that enhance security which are crucial for maintaining a trustworthy journal system. Security-related plugins help protect journals against unauthorised access and spam. Below are examples of such solutions:

- Better Password Plugin – enforces stronger password policies for OJS user accounts, including minimum length and complexity requirements, helping improve the overall security of the system.
- HoneyPot Plugin – this plugin verifies new user registrations by creating a honeypot on the User Registration form (a concealed form field designed to detect and block bots).

Recommendations and good practices when working with plug-ins:

- Update your plugins regularly alongside OJS core updates.
- Test new plugins in a pre-production environment before deploying them.
- Document custom plugin installations to maintain clarity during upgrades.
- Deactivate and remove unused plugins to improve performance and security

Summary

OJS plugins extend and customise the platform's functionality for journal management and publishing. Only administrators can install them, either via the OJS interface or manually. Ensuring compatibility with your OJS version is essential to avoid software issues, and new or external plugins may need separate installation.

Checklist

- Identify which **site-wide** and **journal-specific** plugins are needed.
- Install plugins through the **OJS interface** or manually (administrator only).
- Test new plugins in a **pre-production environment** before deployment.
- Ensure all plugins are **compatible** with the current OJS version.
- Keep plugins **updated** alongside OJS core updates.
- Document **custom plugin installations** for maintenance and upgrades.
- **Deactivate or remove** unused plugins to improve performance and security.
- Consider popular plugins like **CrossRef XML Export, QuickSubmit, Usage Statistics, and DOAJ Export Plugin** for additional functionality.
- Improve security of your OJS instance by adding plugins like **BetterPassword** and **HoneyPot** plugins.

Additional resources

- ❖ PKP Docs - Learning OJS - Plugins:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/learning-ojs/3.3/en/settings-website#plugins>
- ❖ PKP Plugin inventory:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/plugin-inventory/en/>
- ❖ Live plugin gallery list on GitHub:
<https://github.com/pkp/plugin-gallery/blob/main/plugins.xml>
- ❖ PKP Plugin Compatibility list:
<https://pkp.github.io/plugin-compatibility/index.html>
- ❖ OJS Diamond Plugins:
<https://www.craft-oa.eu/ojs-diamond-plugins/>
- ❖ List of recommended plugins (by Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)):
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/105taVgVbi4ve0kAGuYazypa_ZhwUBNBJG7vp_mRFFL68

✓ THEMING

Theming refers to customising the appearance and interface of a journal or a publishing service by applying themes. In the context of OJS, theming is not only about aesthetics, but also about aligning the platform with the visual identity and UX goals of the publishing initiative, whether it's a single journal or a broader institutional publishing service.

A consistent and well-designed visual interface helps users (authors, reviewers, readers, and editors) navigate the platform efficiently and with confidence. It also reinforces the visual identity of the journal or service. This may be particularly relevant for institutional platforms hosting multiple journals, which may want to ensure a recognisable and coherent experience across the site while still allowing individual journals some degree of customisation.

OJS provides several default themes that can be used out of the box. These include:

- **Default Theme** – a clean, modern theme that supports responsiveness and accessibility.
- **Bootstrap 3 Theme** – community-built theme built on the Bootstrap framework, designed to be a base for your child theme.
- **Classic Theme** – theme that relates to more traditional aesthetics.
- Others such as **Health Sciences, Immersion, Manuscript, Pragma**.

These themes are designed with simplicity, accessibility, and academic use in mind, and they can be configured through the OJS UI (e.g., changing colors, fonts, header images) without requiring direct access to code.

Custom Themes

Beyond the default options, OJS supports the development and deployment of **custom themes**. These allow for more advanced visual and functional customisations and are implemented using the OJS plugin architecture and its templating system (primarily based on PHP and Smarty templates). Creating a custom theme enables:

- Alignment with institutional or departmental visual guidelines.
- Integration with third-party design systems.
- Advanced control over layout and component behavior.
- Optimisation for specific UX needs.

To create or install a custom theme, platform managers typically need skills in:

- PHP and OJS plugin development.
- HTML/ Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and front-end frameworks (e.g., Bootstrap, Tailwind).
- Smarty templating language used in OJS.

- Familiarity with OJS's theming hooks and plugin registration system.

Custom themes can be developed in-house or sourced from the broader OJS community.

Considerations and Risks of Custom and Community Themes

1. Upgrade Compatibility

Custom themes may introduce maintenance challenges when upgrading OJS. New OJS versions often modify internal templates, API endpoints, or plugin behavior, which can break custom themes that are not kept up-to-date. Therefore, it's crucial for service providers to:

- Version-control theme code separately.
- Regularly test custom themes before upgrading production.
- Follow OJS release notes for changes affecting themes.

2. Licensing of Community-Contributed Themes

Themes developed by the community and shared on public repositories may use various open-source licenses. When adopting such themes, IPSPs and other institutions must ensure:

- Compatibility with their service's licensing model.
- Compliance with attribution and redistribution requirements.
- Awareness of the maintenance status and responsiveness of the original developers.

3. Security and Performance

Poorly developed themes may negatively affect accessibility, performance, and security (e.g., by improperly loading third-party resources). Institutions should enforce internal review processes and sandbox environments to evaluate external themes.

4. Sustainability and Support

Custom theming requires dedicated technical capacity. For institutions running large-scale or long-term services, it's important to plan for sustainable support – code documentation, maintenance schedule, and knowledge transfer among staff.

Summary

Theming in OJS involves customising the journal or platform appearance to align with visual identity and UX goals. Default themes offer ready-to-use options, while custom or community themes allow advanced personalisation but require programming skills and ongoing maintenance to ensure compatibility, security, and performance.

Checklist

- Decide whether default themes meet your visual and functional needs.
- Consider creating custom themes for institutional branding or specialised UX.
- Ensure technical skills are available for PHP, Smarty templates, and front-end development.
- Version-control custom themes and test them before OJS upgrades.
- Verify licensing and maintenance status when using community-contributed themes.
- Assess potential impacts on accessibility, performance, and security.
- Plan sustainable support, documentation, and knowledge transfer for custom themes.

Additional resources

- ❖ PKP Docs - Designing Your Journal:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/designing-your-journal/en/>
- ❖ PKP Docs - Theming Guide:
<https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/pkp-theming-guide/en/>
- ❖ Meet the experts - Workshop #5 - Theming
 - Talk: <https://doi.org/10.5446/71775>
 - Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17415941>

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8 ANNEX: LODEL

✓ Introduction

Lodel (LOGiciel D'Édition Électronique) is a CMS created to handle long and complex texts as part of a highly structured editorial environment. It has been developed for electronic publishing in the academic field, particularly in the humanities and social sciences.

Lodel is an online software, designed to enable quality academic electronic publishing by editorial teams. Special care has been paid to optimising the time required to publish a document online. The software enables publishing secretaries to publish their texts themselves, in the same way they control publication using Xpress or Indesign, and without having to be a computer specialist.

Created in 2000 by the French CLEO, it was designed to address the specific requirements of scholarly journals and academic book publishing, handling structured content, citations, multilingual texts, and peer-reviewed articles. Lodel adheres closely to academic publishing conventions, such as the proper handling of footnotes, text structure, non-Latin scripts, diacritics, small caps, and non-breaking spaces.

The software is maintained by OpenEdition (formerly CLEO) and supports three of its four platforms: OpenEdition Journals (over 600 journals), OpenEdition Books (over 15,000 books), and Calenda (over 59,000 events). Lodel is widely used by French-speaking academic communities.

✓ Context

A major refactoring of Lodel is currently underway, leading to the development of the new version, Lodel 2.0. However, this version is not yet available as an open-source software (as it is still in active development - October 2025).

Consequently, this toolkit preempts Lodel 2.0's wider release with a full description of the current Lodel 2.0 installation process. Additionally, it includes an introduction and documentation for the "HelloWorld Bundle", which explains and demonstrates how to add new functionalities in Lodel 2.0. This bundle has been developed thanks to the CRAFT-OA project and is already available as an open-source software with a documentation in english.

✓ LODEL 2.0 INSTALLATION PROCESS

This guide provides step-by-step instructions to install, configure, and run a Lodel Standard Edition platform locally. Before proceeding, ensure that your environment meets the required prerequisites and that all necessary dependencies are installed.

The Lodel Standard Edition serves as the foundation for your publishing platform. It's built on the Lodel-skeleton, which uses Lodel as a bundle to provide additional functionalities. The Lodel-skeleton is designed to be distributed as an open-source project, making it a flexible base for various Lodel setups.

1. Requirements

Before installing Lodel Standard Edition, ensure your system meets the following requirements:

- a. Operating System Compatibility: Lodel is recommended for Linux-based systems but can also be installed on macOS or Windows with necessary adjustments.
- b. PHP: Ensure PHP 8.1 or later is installed. Additionally, the following PHP extensions must be enabled: curl, xml, intl, zip, mysqlnd, mbstring, gd, amqp.
- c. Database: MariaDB (Recommended) or MySQL.
- d. Composer version 2.
- e. Node.js (version 12.x) and npm (version 6.*) using nvm
- f. Symfony Command Line Interface (CLI)

2. Platform installation steps

- a. Clone the `lodel-skeleton` repository from GitLab using SSH (main branch) and rename it to your desired project name:

```
$ git clone <lodel-skeleton_repository_url> <project_name>
```

Replace <lodel-skeleton_repository_url> with the actual repository URL.

- b. Move into the newly created project directory and install the required dependencies:

```
$ composer install
```

```
$ npm install
```

```
$ npm run build
```

- c. Create a `.env.local` file and configure the database credentials:


```
DATABASE_URL=mysql://<username>:<password>@localhost/<database_name>?serverVersion=mariadb-10.3.28
```

Replace <username>, <password>, and <database_name> accordingly.

- d. Create the Database running the following command:

```
$ php bin/console doctrine:database:create
```

- e. Install the Platform, specifying a platform name (e.g., my-lodel):

```
$ php bin/console lodel:platform:install <platform_name>
```

- f. Migrate legacy platform data to ensure that existing platform data is migrated to the new structure:

```
$ php bin/console lodel:migrations:platform:migrate legacy_platform
```

- g. Generate an administrator account for the platform:

```
$ php bin/console lodel:platform:create_admin
```

- h. Launch the local development server accessible on <http://localhost:8000>:

```
$ symfony server:start
```

- i. Access the application by opening your browser and navigating to:

- i. Main application: <http://localhost:8000>
- ii. Login page: <http://localhost:8000/login>

Use the credentials for the admin user created earlier to log in.

✓ LODEL 2.0 HELLO WORLD BUNDLE

A Lodel 2.0 bundle is the equivalent of an OJS plugin, both extending the platform's functionalities in a modular way; the term "bundle" comes from Symfony, the framework behind Lodel 2.0.

Thanks to the CRAFT-OA Project, a Lodel Hello World Bundle has been developed as part of Lodel Toolkit. It is a starter bundle designed to help developers quickly create custom extensions for the Lodel platform. It has been developed thanks to CRAFT-OA support. It provides the basic setup and features needed to implement new functionality, similar to plugin systems found in other CMS platforms. This allows for quick, efficient addition of features tailored to your Lodel installation.

Github repository	https://github.com/operas-eu/lodel-helloworld-bundle
Video demonstration (in english)	https://api.nakala.fr/embed/10.34847/nkl.0d599t8f/735937ff99910cbeeb77f635574c93e2e8e00e10
Code Review	Nicolas Vernot-Cortes (Lodel 2 Lead Developer)
Comments	Lodel2 source code is not yet available. For this reason, the bundle can not be tested externally to OpenEdition for the moment. That's why a demonstration video has been made.
Status	Released
Documentation (in english)	https://lodel-helloworld-bundle.readthedocs.io/en/latest/

Table 5: Lodel2 Helloword bundle ID card

1. Bundle repository and documentation

The source code and generated documentation are available at :

```
<lodel-hello-world-bundle_repository_url> = "https://github.com/operas-eu/lodel-helloworld-bundle"
```

”

```
<lodel-hello-world-bundle_documentation_url> = "https://lodel-helloworld-bundle.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html"
```

2. Requirements

Before installing the Lodel Hello World Bundle, ensure that your environment meets the following requirements:

- a. PHP: Version 8.1 or higher (can be adjusted if necessary)
- b. Symfony: Version 6.4 (Long-Term Support (LTS)) (can be modified as needed)

3. Installation

To install the Lodel Hello World Bundle, follow these steps:

- c. From the root directory of your Lodel application, declare the repository source:

```
$ composer config repositories.lodel/lodel-hello-world-bundle vcs <lodel-hello-world-bundle_repository_url>
```

Replace <lodel-hello-world-bundle_repository_url> with the actual URL of the repository.

- d. Add the dependency to your project by running:

```
$ composer require lodel/lodel-hello-world-bundle:dev-main
```

- e. In most cases, the bundle will be automatically enabled and ready to use without any further configuration. However, if you need to enable the bundle manually, ensure that it is registered in the `config/bundles.php` file as follows:

```
Lodel\HelloWorldBundle\HelloWorldBundle::class => ['all' => true],
```

4. Tests

This bundle includes a basic test suite to verify that the core functionality works as expected. To run the tests, execute the following command:

```
$ ./vendor/bin/phpunit
```

5. Documentation generation

The Lodel Hello World Bundle uses Doxygen to generate code documentation. Doxygen reads through the PHPDoc comments in the codebase and produces well-organised, browsable HTML documentation.

- a. Install Doxygen on your system:

```
$ sudo apt-get install doxygen
```

- b. Once Doxygen is installed, navigate to the root directory of your project and generate the documentation by running:

```
$ doxygen Doxyfile
```

This will create the documentation in the `docs/html/` directory. You can then open the `index.html` file in your web browser to view the documentation. Remember to regenerate the documentation whenever you update the codebase by running the above steps again.

